

SmartCHP
COGENERATING A RENEWABLE FUTURE

D5.3

Consumer and social acceptance assessment report

Project Number: 815259

Start date of the project: 1st June 2019 – (54 months)

www.smartchp.eu

D5.3 – Consumer and public acceptance assessment report		
Deliverable number	D5.3	
Responsible partner	EEEC	
Due date of deliverable	30 September 2022	
Actual submission date	1 November 2022	
Version	1.0	
Authors	B. Davidis, M. Vis, C. Alasis, M. Maachi Haddou	
Reviewers	B. Davidis, M. Vis, C. Alasis, M. Maachi Haddou	
Work package no.	5	
Work package title	Environmental impact and socio-economic studies	
Work package leader	EEEC	
Work package participants	BTG	
Dissemination level (please select one)		
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium including the Commission Services	
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants, including the Commission Services	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium including the Commission Services	
Nature of the deliverable (please select one)		
R	Report	X
D	Demonstrator	
W	Websites, patents filing, etc	
O	Other	

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Successful implementation of bioenergy systems such as SmartCHP can be supported by understanding the social acceptance of bioenergy CHP and/or bioenergy systems in general in a given country. In this report, the social acceptance of bioenergy systems has been assessed within five relevant focus countries in the EU, i.e. Sweden, Netherlands, Romania, Croatia and Greece.

(Wüstenhagen, Wolsink, & Bürer, 2007) describes the concept of 'social acceptance' and proposes an interdisciplinary and three-dimensional approach to social acceptance.

- Socio-political acceptance which refers to how policies and technologies are perceived by political stakeholders and the broader public.
- Community acceptance which is particularly relevant in case bioenergy projects are constructed in a community, where local stakeholders and residents have the right to oppose to such a project.
- Market acceptance, or the diffusion of innovation, that explains the adoption of innovative technologies by consumers by means of communication between adopter and their environment.

In this report we have used the above-described three dimensions and assessed the social acceptance of Smart-CHP systems by literature and media analysis. In our approach, the latter were to be supplemented by interviews with key stakeholders identified in the focus countries, but the response rate was too low to allow for taking the results into account. We also assessed the main interactions between the three dimensions of social acceptance, in particular how socio-political acceptance and community acceptance have impact on market acceptance.

Socio-political acceptance

In order to assess socio-political acceptance a policy analysis and a media analysis using the SPEED framework has been performed. The media has a critical and influential role regarding socio-political acceptance of energy projects through framing. SPEED acknowledges that energy deployment occurs within energy systems that are not only influenced by technological capacity and resource availability, but also by economic, political, cultural, health and safety, and environmental factors. To characterize public discourse on bio-CHP and/or bioenergy in general in the five focus countries, the content and framing in bio-CHP and/or bioenergy related articles from 2017 to 2021 in the largest circulating newspapers in the five focus countries were analysed. Although the number of articles and risk/benefit statements on bioenergy differs considerably between the five focus countries, it is possible to compare the sentiments regarding bioenergy by analysing the distribution of risk and benefit statements between the categories of the SPEED framework.

Table 1-1 shows the media coverage of statements between the categories of the SPEED framework, including both risk and benefit statements. Please note that neutral statements have been left out to keep the analysis straightforward. The environmental frame is used most frequently in the Netherlands and Sweden and is dominant in Romania as well. In Croatia and Greece, the economic frame is used most often. In all countries the political frame is used frequently, related to meeting renewable energy and GHG targets and policy frameworks. Technical frames are

used regularly in Greece and Croatia but are (nearly) absent in the Netherlands, Sweden, and Romania. The cultural frame is hardly used. Except for home heating (firewood) bioenergy which usually does not interfere with the daily life of people.

Table 1-1: Media coverage per SPEED frame (risks and benefits)

SPEED frame	Netherlands	Sweden	Croatia	Romania	Greece	Average
Cultural	1%	0%	3%	4%	0%	1%
Economic	4%	1%	38%	19%	35%	19%
Environmental	71%	72%	20%	48%	18%	46%
Health & Safety	10%	1%	5%	0%	18%	7%
Political	13%	25%	20%	26%	6%	18%
Technical	2%	0%	15%	4%	24%	9%
Total	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Table 1-2 shows that the total use of risk statements differs widely per focus country from 82% of all statements in the Netherlands to only 12% in Greece. In all countries most risks statements are found in the environmental frame, but again in a varying degree. 64% of all statements used in the Netherlands are in the environmental risk frame, compared to only 6% in Greece. In Romania risk statements in the political frame were found more often than in the other focus countries. These statements cover various themes related to EU and national legislation, for example (fake) news that Romanian households would have to give up wood stoves by 2023 because of a deal with the EU. Statements covering technical and cultural risks were only identified in a few news articles.

Table 1-2: Media coverage per SPEED frame (only risks)

SPEED frame	Netherlands	Sweden	Croatia	Romania	Greece	Average
Cultural	1%	0%	0%	4%	0%	1%
Economic	3%	0%	0%	0%	0%	1%
Environmental	64%	43%	13%	30%	6%	31%
Health & Safety	10%	1%	5%	0%	6%	5%
Political	1%	10%	8%	26%	0%	9%
Technical	2%	0%	0%	4%	0%	1%
Total	82%	55%	25%	63%	12%	47%

Table 1-3 highlights the distribution of beneficial statements between countries and SPEED frames. In general, the economic and environmental benefits dominate. Especially in Croatia and Greece economic benefits are found in news articles on bioenergy, while in Sweden and Netherlands these benefits are hardly discussed¹. In Sweden next to environmental risks, the benefits are discussed as well, while in the Netherlands the environmental benefits are covered only to a limited degree.

¹ It is noted that the analysis of Sweden and Netherlands was done before the invasion of Ukraine, while the other countries include the period of October 2021 – April 2022 with high fossil energy prices.

Table 1-3: Media coverage per SPEED frame (only benefits)

SPEED frame	Netherlands	Sweden	Croatia	Romania	Greece	Average
Cultural	0%	0%	3%	0%	0%	1%
Economic	1%	1%	38%	19%	35%	19%
Environmental	6%	29%	8%	19%	12%	15%
Health & Safety	0%	0%	0%	0%	12%	2%
Political	11%	14%	13%	0%	6%	9%
Technical	0%	0%	15%	0%	24%	8%
Total	18%	45%	75%	37%	88%	53%

Based on the analysis performed, it is expected that it is possible to introduce SmartCHP technology without major social acceptance issues in Sweden, Croatia, Greece, and Romania. The socio-political acceptance of bioenergy is very low in the Netherlands, making it - from a social acceptance point of view - a less attractive country for market introduction of SmartCHP technology.

Community acceptance

Due to the low response to the interviews, within the scope of this study, it was not possible to define a community acceptance strategy at country level.

In order to promote community acceptance in general, the SmartCHP systems have to be designed in such a way that it generates low noise (insulation of engine), low odour (vapour return system during unloading pyrolysis oil), low emissions (emission reduction equipment), and low visibility (modest chimney, underground tank). The storage tank should have the size of at least one truck load avoiding traffic movements. This way the NIMBY effect and related distributional justice issues can be minimised. Procedural justice, e.g. fair permit procedures, depends partly on the permitting process of the concerned country. However, it is generally advised to communicate in a fair way - and in an early stage of the permit process - with the neighbouring community about the plans to install a SmartCHP system, and its impacts.

Market acceptance

Market acceptance involves a wide range of factors, including the discussed socio-political and community related aspects as depicted in Figure 1-1. Socio-political acceptance influences the expectations of potential buyers and users of SmartCHP system, and at the same time impacts the availability of financial support mechanisms. Community acceptance is a prerequisite for a smooth permit procedure.

Decision makers and users need to see the environmental, social, hedonic, and financial benefits from the use of SmartCHP technology. The biomass source of the pyrolysis oil determines an important part of the perceived environmental benefit. It should be clear that no stemwood/whole trees were used to produce pyrolysis oil. Being a legal prerequisite of the RED II, sustainability certification of pyrolysis oil can also be used to support the market acceptance of pyrolysis oil. Social and hedonic benefits related to personal interest of the decision maker/user, social status, feel good, may be less relevant than in the consumer market, but will definitely play a role. Promotional aspects, positioning the user as being a pioneer,

showing that the organisation cares for the environment, can form important motivations to use SmartCHP technologies. A good-looking design can create the desire to own a system.

Figure 1-1: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.

Social acceptance and market introduction strategy

During and after the market introduction phase, the above mentioned socio-political, community and market acceptance factors need to be taken into account. Moreover, since SmartCHP is a new technology, requiring a rather large investment, next to hedonic and normative motivations, there is a strong need for facts enabling a rational decision making. Therefore, it is advised to make information on the product available in a visually attractive brochure and on several websites. Specific information could be developed to address possible worries, fears and scepticisms that can arise with potential users of innovative technologies such as SmartCHP. Under attractive conditions, a number of, say, 3 – 5 pilot projects could be installed, and their performance carefully monitored. Some of the demonstrated installations should permanently be accessible for visits by interested decision makers and potential users, enabling them to see and touch the system.

Once the demonstration has been running smoothly for a year or more, a marketing campaign could be started for the most promising target groups from the identified subsectors, i.e., from the tertiary, industrial, residential and agriculture sector. The campaign should be well organised involving the SmartCHP system manufacturer, 2-3 installation companies that have been trained to install SmartCHP equipment, and possibly the pyrolysis oil producer. The marketing campaign can be developed by a marketing firm, coordinated by a dedicated marketer with a small team that has the overview on the messages and their distribution channels. It is advised to maintain a high service level especially during the first years after market introduction and to develop a strategy to cope with critical questions on

sustainability, for example setting up and maintaining a list of possible questions and answers on the sustainability of the system and used fuel. Involvement of policy makers is important to ensure that SmartCHP technology becomes a common element in renewable energy plans of national and regional authorities. This paves the way for support in the implementation phase, which could be financial support (e.g. subsidies on installations), being part of renewable energy promotion campaigns, and support in solving administrative and legal issues. Finally, it is advised to get involved in local and regional renewable energy promotion platforms, as they can support the introduction of the Smart CHP technology.

List of Abbreviations

BECCS	Bioenergy Carbon Capture & Storage
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CHP	Combined Heat & Power
EASAC	European Academies Science Advisory Council
EC	European Commission
FPBO	Fast Pyrolysis Bio-Oil
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
VPL	Virtual Plant Location

CONTENT

PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY	3
List of Abbreviations	8
TABLES & FIGURES	10
1. Introduction	12
1.1 Background	12
1.2 Objective	12
1.3 Approach	13
1.4 This report	13
2. Methodology.....	14
2.1 Socio-political acceptance	14
2.2 Community acceptance.....	17
2.3 Market acceptance	18
2.4 Stakeholders’ interviews	19
3. Analysis	21
3.1 Policy and media analysis of socio-political acceptance	21
3.1.1 The Netherlands	21
3.1.2 Sweden	28
3.1.3 Croatia	34
3.1.4 Romania	38
3.1.5 Greece.....	42
3.2 Literature analysis of Community acceptance	47
3.3 Literature analysis of Market acceptance	51
3.4 Interviews with stakeholders	58
3.4.1 Results of the requests for interviews in the 5 focus countries	58
3.4.2 Analysis	58
4. Public acceptance strategy	62
4.1 Socio-Political acceptance	62
4.2 Community acceptance.....	63
4.3 Market acceptance	64
4.4 Market introduction strategy.....	66
5. Annex I.....	68
6. Annex II	70

TABLES & FIGURES

Figure 1-1: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.	6
Figure 3-1: The number of articles concerning bioenergy published in Dutch newspapers in the period 2017-2021, subdivided in positive, neutral, and negative articles including related key 'trigger events'. DHoR: Dutch House of Representatives	24
Figure 3-2: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 174 articles assessed in the Dutch media from 2017 to 2021	26
Figure 3-3: The number of articles concerning bioenergy published in the Swedish newspaper Dagens Nyheter in the period 2017-2021, subdivided in positive, neutral, and negative articles including related key 'trigger events'.	30
Figure 3-4: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 69 articles assessed in the Swedish media from 2017 to 2021.....	33
Figure 3-5: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 27 articles assessed in the Croatian media from January 2018 to April 2022	37
Figure 3-6: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 16 articles assessed in the Romanian media from January 2018 to April 2022	42
Figure 3-7: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 42 articles assessed in the Greek media from January 2018 to April 2022.....	46
Figure 3-8: Rank acceptability indices for RET alternatives, showing the variety of possible preferences that place alternatives on different ranks. Alternatives are sorted according to their first rank acceptability index. Source: Jung et al. (2016)	48
Figure 3-9: perceived importance of factors related to consumers' behavior, preferences and attitudes for residential microgeneration technologies. Source: Karytsas et al. (2019).....	56
Figure 3-10: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.	57
Figure 4-1: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.	62

Table 1-1: Media coverage per SPEED frame (risks and benefits)	4
Table 1-2: Media coverage per SPEED frame (only risks)	4
Table 1-3: Media coverage per SPEED frame (only benefits)	5
Table 2-1: Descriptions of SPEED risk and benefit frames.	15
Table 2-2: Keywords used to identify relevant news articles	16
Table 2-3: Overview of the consulted newspaper per focus country.	17
Table 3-1: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Dutch news articles on bioenergy.	27
Table 3-2: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Swedish news articles on bioenergy.	34
Table 3-3: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Croatian news articles on bioenergy.	38
Table 3-4: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Romanian news articles on bioenergy.	42
Table 3-5: List of concerns of communities on implementation of bioenergy projects and estimated relevance for community acceptance SmartCHP.	50
Table 3-6: Barriers to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.	52
Table 3-7: Motivations to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.	52
Table 3-8: Other influencing factors to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.	53
Table 3-9: Interview request' response rate by country	58
Table 3-10: Number and type of respondents by country	58

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

As part of the European Union's ambition to be completely climate-neutral by 2050, one of the goals set to significantly reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions as a result of energy production. One component in realizing such a goal is to phase out fossil-based energy production technology and substitute these technologies with renewable energy production technologies. Energy produced from biomass represented 58% of the EU's renewable energy consumption (and 9% of all energy sources)² as of 2018. To further increase the amount of renewable energy, adaptation of bioenergy technologies, such as SmartCHP, is essential.

Few studies have investigated the public opinion of bioenergy in general, compared to that of other renewable energy technologies such as wind or solar energy (Carley, Konisky, Atiq, & Land, 2020). Despite the associated GHG emission reduction potential (Baležentis, Streimikiene, Zhang, & Liobikiene, 2019), the public backing of such activities from society is not self-evident. Among the various forms of renewable energy, bioenergy ranks relatively low in terms of public acceptance in many European countries (Schumacher, Krones, McKenna, & Schultmann, 2019). This observed low public acceptance may be a result of a lack of awareness concerning the benefits of bioenergy and/or a lack of trust in stakeholders who decide to increase the adoption rate of bioenergy technologies (Fytli & Zabaniotou, 2017). Ultimately, fierce public opposition to bioenergy projects can potentially result in a termination of that project. This demonstrates how a lack of public acceptance can impede the transition from energy production of fossil-based sources to renewable sources. Hence, a better understanding of public acceptance concerning bioenergy production is perceived to be critical in order to fully realize the transition towards renewable energy, and thereby achieve the EU's overall goal of climate neutrality by 2050.

1.2 Objective

The overall objective of the *SmartCHP* project is the realization of a cost-effective and flexible energy system by using a liquid intermediate energy carrier in an efficient diesel-engine based Combined Heat and Power (CHP) unit.

Successful implementation of such bioenergy system requires full understanding of the public acceptance concerning bioenergy CHP and/or bioenergy in general. In this report, the social acceptance of SmartCHP will be assessed within five relevant focus countries in the EU as social acceptance can vary considerably between countries. The following focus countries have been identified by the *SmartCHP* consortium partners, which play an important role in other *SmartCHP* tasks within WP2 (biomass and fast pyrolysis oil production), WP5 (Environmental impact and socio-economic studies) and WP6 (Market assessment, business development and case studies):

- Sweden, North EU (softwood forestry residues)
- Netherlands, West EU (Pyrolysis oil import scenario)
- Romania, East EU (Corn stover)
- Croatia, Central EU (Miscanthus)

² Bioenergy Europe Statistical Report, Report Bioheat 2020

- Greece, South EU (Olive kernel wood)

There is a decent geographical spread of countries in the EU and therefore representative for the different EU-regions.

1.3 Approach

Social acceptance is an important factor to consider in the deployment of a smartCHP system or any other technology that the public interacts with on a regular basis. In the last decade, there has been a growing interest in the concept of social acceptance, especially in relation to the transition from fossil-based sources to renewable energy sources. In the more general sense, (Wüstenhagen, Wolsink, & Bürer, 2007) describes the concept of 'social acceptance' and proposes an interdisciplinary and three-dimensional approach to social acceptance. Firstly, **socio-political acceptance** is the most general dimension, which refers to how policies and technologies are perceived by political stakeholders and the broader public. **Community acceptance** is the second dimension which is particularly relevant in case bioenergy projects are constructed in a community, where local stakeholders and residents have the rights to oppose to such a project. Lastly, **market acceptance**, or the diffusion of innovation, explains the adoption of innovative technologies by consumers by means of communication between adopter and their environment.

Using the above-described three dimensions, the social acceptance of Smart-CHP systems is assessed by literature and media analysis, followed by interviews with key stakeholders, as further elaborated in chapter 2.

Social acceptance strategy

Ultimately, the assessment of all three social acceptance dimensions results in a strategy to ensure or even increase consumer and public acceptance, including the formulation of key messages, explicitly taking into account the views of different stakeholders and selection of associated dissemination pathways in order to create maximum impact. The strategy will serve as input to the socio-economic impact assessment (T5.4), marketing activities for technology introduction (WP6), and for designing proper communication strategies in WP7.

1.4 This report

In chapter 2 the methodology to assess the three dimensions of social acceptance in the frame of SmartCHP is further elaborated and discussed. Chapter 3 shows the results of the assessment. Chapter 4 shows the social acceptance strategy.

2. Methodology

2.1 Socio-political acceptance

Introduction

(Wüstenhagen et al., 2007) states that barriers for achieving successful projects at the implementation level can be considered as manifestation of lack of social acceptance. At the level of socio-political acceptance, this concerns the acceptance by policy actors of effective policies. Such policies require the institutionalization of frameworks that effectively foster market and community acceptance. In general, energy related policies are embedded within competing country specific priorities for resources and attention, making political saliency critical. It is therefore important to assess political saliency towards bioenergy, and on the basis thereof determine the political commitment in each focus country.

Other studies, like that of (Peters, Axsen, & Mallett, 2018) define socio-political acceptance as general acceptance by citizens (or the public), which in turn can be guided by and represented through the media and key stakeholders (i.e., framing). Clearly, citizens have the right to vote for governments that implement policy and constitute a great part of potential consumers of the bioenergy produced. Yet, citizens may also form sub-groups of opposition that can take social action. Citizen opposition or support can be influenced by their beliefs and perceptions regarding the risks and benefits of specific projects.

For each focus country socio-political acceptance of Smart-CHP is assessed by a combination of policy analysis, media analysis and interviews. The level of socio-political acceptance of bio-CHP and bioenergy in general will be identified and serve as proxy for the expected acceptance of SmartCHP technology. The policy assessment and media review will be supplemented with interviews (by EEEEC) with policy makers and NGOs, to assess their estimation of the socio-political acceptance of SmartCHP. Questionnaires will be developed and used to guide interviews and ensure uniform coverage of subjects in all cases.

Policy analysis

Political commitment is an important factor regarding bioenergy projects. At this point, such projects require long-term and stable policies as well as reliable financial support systems in order to achieve successful implementation. As such, to fully understand socio-political acceptance regarding smartCHP systems, a policy analysis will be performed to characterize the political commitment towards bio-CHP systems and/or bioenergy in general in all five focus countries. The policy analysis characterises the political commitment of the focus countries towards the implementation of bioenergy projects in order to reach their country specific environmental policy goals.

Media analysis using the SPEED framework

The media has a critical and influential role regarding socio-political acceptance of energy projects through **framing**. Frames are a means through which people attempt to understand unfamiliar and complex concepts through their own experiences and predispositions (Nisbet, 2009). The concept of framing is thus of particular interest when analysing news media since news media both reflects and influences societal discourse about bioenergy technologies and/or bioenergy in general, and consequently can shape citizen and stakeholder perceptions as such.

As a result, frames can either favour or hinder the deployment of bioenergy technologies as well as the frameworks used in their deployment. As an example, research has observed how changes in framing have influenced the rise in support for bioenergy in Finland (Kivimaa & Mickwitz, 2011).

To assess media framing, the enhanced Socio-Political Evaluation of Energy Deployment (SPEED) framework was utilized (Stephens, Peterson, & Wilson, 2014). SPEED acknowledges that energy deployment occurs within energy systems that are not only influenced by technological capacity and resource availability, but also by economic, political, cultural, health and safety, and environmental factors (Langheim et al., 2014). Each type of factor has the potential for both negative and positive associations, for generating perceived risks and benefits to the larger social system. In respect to bio-CHP or bioenergy in general, these SPEED categories help to understand how the public and key stakeholders are responding to and or shape bioenergy and bioenergy related policy deployment. Hence, the analysis focused on the framing of bio-CHP and/or bioenergy risks and benefits in the selected articles characterizing the frequency of technical, economic, political, health and safety, environmental, and cultural frames (Table 2-1).

Table 2-1: Descriptions of SPEED risk and benefit frames.

SPEED frame	Benefit	Risk
Technical	Engineering advancements; interactions to create new opportunities	Potential negative technical aspects of system change; needs or vulnerabilities
Economic	Strengthen the economy (jobs, manufacturing); saving money	Increased costs to different actors; increased economic uncertainty or financial risk
Political	Positive political ramifications (e.g., energy independence, energy security, etc.)	Negative political ramifications (e.g., public frustrations and difficult legal and regulatory processes)
Health and Safety	Reduced respiratory problems from improved air quality	Health and safety concerns associated with bioenergy
Environmental	Reduced GHGs or carbon emissions; mitigation of and adaption to climate change; less air and water pollution	Potential threat to human or ecological health (e.g., threats to protected species and habitat disruption)
Cultural	Positive behavioural change	Concerns of privacy; perceived negative impacts on way of life

To characterize public discourse on bio-CHP and/or bioenergy in general in the five focus countries, the content and framing in bio-CHP and/or bioenergy related articles from 2017 to 2021 in the largest circulating newspapers in the five focus countries were analysed. Table 2-2 summarizes the keywords that were used to retrieve relevant articles for the analysis. The keywords "biomass" and "bioenergy" appeared to be the best keywords to obtain relevant articles from newspapers.

Table 2-2: Keywords used to identify relevant news articles

English	Dutch	Swedish	Croatian	Romanian	Greek (cyrillic)	Greek (Roman)
Bioenergy	Bioenergie	Bioenergi	Bio energija	Bioenergie	Βιο ενέργεια	Vio enérgeia
Biomass	Biomassa	Biomassa	Biomasa	Biomasă	Βιομάζα	Viomáza
Combined heat and power (CHP)	Warmtekracht koppeling (WKK)	Kraftvärme	Kombinirana toplina i energija	Puterea și puterea combinate	Συνδυασμένη θερμότητα και ισχύς	Syndyasméni thermótita kai ischýs
Pyrolysis oil	Pyrolyse-olie	Pyrolysolja	Ulje za pirolizu	Ulei de piroliză	Λάδι πυρόλυσης	Ládi pyrólýsis
Energy transition	Energietransitie	Energiövärgång	Prijelaz energije	Tranziția energetică	Ενεργειακή μετάβαση	Energieiakí metávasi
Energy	energie	energi	energije	energie	ενέργεια	enérgeia

Table 2-3 shows which newspapers have been consulted, their weekly reach, and the total number of analysed news articles per country. Specific articles on bio-CHP and/or bioenergy in the Netherlands were found using LexisNexis® Newsdesk database, which provides access to all newspapers, and searched on print media published between 2017 and 2021. Unfortunately, and unexpectedly, Lexis Nexis did not give access to newspapers in the other focus countries. For these, articles had to be found by checking main newspapers per country without the support of LexisNexis. For Sweden, an online paid subscription to *Dagens Nyheter* provided access to 69 relevant articles on biomass related topics, sufficient to make a chronological description of the course of the bioenergy discussion in Sweden. In case of Romania, Croatia and Greece, free access could be obtained to the news articles which has the advantage that direct links could be provided to the articles. The number of articles found with the keyword “biomass” and “bioenergy” that were related to bioenergy was more limited in these countries. Therefore, no chronological description of the media sentiment could be made.

The lower number of articles found on bioenergy in the Croatian, Romanian and Greek media may partly be a result of the limitations of manual searching of articles with simple keyword search at the website of the newspaper, compared to the use of advanced Lexis Nexis tools as applied to analyse the newspapers in the Netherlands.

Table 2-3: Overview of the consulted newspaper per focus country³.

Country	Newspaper	Weekly reach (TV, Radio, Print)	# of articles analysed
Netherlands	<i>Six national newspapers through LexisNexis</i>	18%	174
	<i>Algemeen Dagblad</i>	18%	
	<i>De Telegraaf,</i>	9%	
	<i>De Volkskrant,</i>	n.d.	
	<i>Trouw, NRC NEXT, Het Financieel Dagblad</i>		
Sweden	<i>Dagens Nyheter</i>	9%	69
Romania	<i>Libertatea</i>	18%	16
	<i>Adevarul</i>	18%	
	<i>Evenimentul Zilei</i>	n.d.	
	<i>Romanian Journal</i>	n.d.	
Croatia	<i>24sata</i>	36%	27
	<i>Jutarnji list</i>	29%	
	<i>Vecernji list</i>	18%	
Greece	<i>Kathimerini</i>	17%	42
	<i>Ta Nea</i>	13%	
	<i>To Vima</i>	13%	

2.2 Community acceptance

Community acceptance involves the magnitude to which decisions regarding permits and land use are accepted by local residents and authorities, the way in which policymaking is carried out and the way charges and gains are shared within the community. Generally speaking, although various opinion polls have shown that people are highly supportive towards expanding clean energy sources⁴, proposed energy schemes will be immediately confronted to local opposition, and ultimately, end up being postponed or even cancelled (Walker, 1995). Understanding how local citizens form their own perceptions, and what factors are likely to shape these latter, may then contribute to implementing renewable energy projects better, taking into consideration affected community members' perceptions. Therefore, a literature analysis will be performed to characterize the factors influencing community acceptance of bioenergy, supplemented with interviews.

The level of community acceptance of bio-CHP projects and bioenergy projects in general as proxy for the SmartCHP technology will be estimated by literature analysis.

³ Weekly outreach (% of country specific population) is based on a survey conducted by Reuters institute for the study of journalism in collaboration with the University of Oxford.

Source: <https://www.digitalnewsreport.org/survey/2020/country-and-market-data-2020/>

⁴ McGowan F, Sauter R. Public opinion on energy research: a desk study for the research councils. Brighton, United Kingdom: Sussex Energy Group, SPRU, University of Sussex; 2005

2.3 Market acceptance

Market acceptance is the third dimension within the concept of social acceptance. Whereas socio-political acceptance and community acceptance mostly concern “acceptance in principal”, market acceptance in addition concerns “acceptance in actual adoption and use” (Heiskanen et al 2012)⁵. This dimension strives to understand the various factors that drive or inhibit customers to accept implementation and use of a smartCHP system that is being developed in the *SmartCHP* project. In general, these customers are the private and public owners of buildings and investors in this equipment. Wüstenhagen points out that lessons can be learned from the literature on diffusion of innovation (Rogers 1995), however acknowledging that energy technologies continue to be bound to infrastructures that make them inherently more complex for diffusion of innovation than other products.

Within the EU project Residue2Heat, the market acceptance factors of small-scale pyrolysis oil heating in the capacity of 20 -200 kW were studied in detail (Vis, 2018). While Vis (2018) focused on market acceptance of homeowners, many of the market acceptance factors are expected to be relevant for potential buyers of SmartCHP systems (in the range of 250 – 2500 kW_{input}) as well. This assumption will be tested during interviews with potential end users, to be carried out in parallel with the development of business cases (Task 6.4).

While Wüstenhagen et al. did not elaborate much on the interaction of the three dimensions of social acceptance, these interactions do exist. Focussing on market acceptance as end point, it can be expected that socio-political acceptance and community acceptance impact market acceptance.

Literature analysis

The market acceptance assessment will build on a literature analysis, including a recent overview assessment of market acceptance of small-scale pyrolysis systems at homeowner level (Vis 2018), complemented with relevant literature on market acceptance of renewable energy technologies at building and company level. The literature overview provides insight in critical factors that may also affect the decision making of envisaged end users of SmartCHP systems.

Relevant market acceptance factors identified by Vis (2018) were:

- motivating factors such as saving money, environmental motivations, security of supply, personal interest in renewable energy;
- barriers such as high capital costs, difficulties to integrate the equipment in the building, hassle of installation, uncertainty about reliability and performance, worries about ease of use; and
- other influencing factors, such as awareness of the existence of pyrolysis oil as renewable energy option, income, age and social class of the owners.

The market study (Smart CHP Deliverable D6.1) has identified a number of relevant market segments and their market potential:

- Tertiary sector, including hotels, hospitals, office buildings, retail (e.g. shopping malls), educational buildings, (primary and secondary schools,

⁵ H.K. Eva Heiskanen, Kaisa Matschoss, Report on Specific Features of Public and Social Acceptance and Perception of Nearly Zero - Energy Buildings and Renewable Heating and Cooling in Europe with a Specific Focus on the Target Countries, Intelligent Energy Europe, 2012.

- high schools and universities, research laboratories, professional training activities and others), etc.
- Industrial sector, including food and beverage, pulp and paper, chemical, refining, ferrous and nonferrous metals, non-metallic minerals, pharmaceuticals, etc.
- Residential sector, including small-scale District Heating / Cooling, large residential complexes, social housing, etc.
- Agriculture sector, including greenhouses.

Decision making at household level is rather straightforward, as only a few persons are involved. Similarly, small business owners may have the possibility to decide to invest or not. In case of larger business, or subsidiary branches of a group, e.g., a multinational or a hotel chain, one may need to convince the energy engineer, the sustainability manager, and the general manager, after which the head office needs to give green light. Housing co-operations may have a decision structure requiring to consult their tenants, while homeowner associations of e.g., an apartment building may need to reach consensus before any decision can be made. Due to these differences in decision making, the market acceptance factors on potential buyers of SmartCHP systems may differ from those of households, which will be checked during the interviews.

2.4 Stakeholders' interviews

Rationale and process

In order to complement the literature, policy and media review and analysis, the organization of interviews is highly relevant to better understand and define the level of social acceptance of the technology in the five SmartCHP focus countries, i.e., Sweden, Netherlands, Croatia, Romania, and Greece that were selected among others based on their suitability for pyrolysis oil production, with the exception of the Netherlands being a market for imported pyrolysis oil.

It was decided to have semi structured interviews instead of a survey. Pyrolysis oil combustion in SmartCHP systems is a new technology not yet available on the market and most end users are not familiar with it. In most cases it needs to be introduced at the start of the interview. At this stage, qualitative information is more important than quantitative information based on a large survey. Moreover, we expect a very low response from a survey on this topic.

With regard to the Socio-political acceptance, key stakeholders such as governments, industry groups, non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are of great importance as they may try to act in the public interest and/or influence public opinion either positively or negatively as governmental and proponent activities can also stimulate opposition. Such stakeholders often have pre-established motivations for an energy project linked to their perception of its risks and benefits and their affiliated organization's mandate. These stakeholders can directly influence an energy project's design and implementation strategy and at the same time can influence how media and the general public perceive and frame energy issues (van Alphen, van Voorst tot Voorst, Hekkert, & Smits, 2007). Depending on the responses to the requests for interviews, it could allow for characterizing their perception and how they frame the risks and benefits of bio-CHP systems and/or bioenergy in general.

Community acceptance will also be assessed based on interviews with key stakeholders such as municipalities, and Civil Society Organizations and non-

governmental organizations (NGOs). The viewpoints from potential buyers will be obtained, especially related to the permit procedures needed to start a SmartCHP unit.

Finally, concerning the Market acceptance, it will be evaluated based on interviews with potential end-users identified during the project implementation in the five focus countries.

The list of key stakeholders which were contacted for interviews for all five countries is presented in Annex 1.

Questionnaire structure

The questionnaire was generally designed in order to address the following main factors:

1. Awareness:
 - a. Knowledge of the environmental and energy issues (pollution, energy consumption, etc.)
 - b. Energy production and distribution issues perception
 - c. Knowledge of the technology and regulations
 - d. Efficacy of the technology
2. Local Context influencing decision making:
 - a. Policy context : EU, National and Local policies
 - b. Social norms and influence
 - c. Drivers: Facilitating conditions (incentives, etc.)
 - d. Perceived barriers, risks and benefits

For the case of municipalities, additional questions were prepared to tackle specific issues such as the experience with local production of RE, local community's acceptance, permitting issues, etc.

The questionnaire consists of open questions and for the case of barriers, options are given. It is presented in Annex II.

Interview process

After sending out the requests for interviews and following the receipt of positive responses. The interviewees were provided with a short and simplified presentation of the project highlighting its main features.

The interviews were setup in two parts, the first one was introductory, going over the presentation and presenting the project in brief again in case there was no time for the interviewee to go through it in prior or in case they had any questions about it. The second part consisted in going over the questions one by one and in some cases where a question would trigger a broader answer covering another question, it was noted by the interviewer.

Once the interviews took an end, a follow up email was sent to the interested interviewees with more information about the project and/or information about the next meetings and events that they could attend.

Once all interviews are conducted, the results can be processed, and – depending on the outcome - to some extent differences between segments and countries could be identified. These interpretations have to be made with care as the number of interviews per country turned out to be very limited as initially foreseen. (See analysis part (Section 3.4).

3. Analysis

3.1 Policy and media analysis of socio-political acceptance

This chapter shows the results of the social political acceptance assessment using policy analysis and media analysis of the five focus countries, i.e., Netherlands, Sweden, Romania, Croatia and Greece.

3.1.1 The Netherlands

Policy analysis

In 2013, several Dutch stakeholders (government, unions, and environmental organizations) signed the Dutch Social Economic Council (SER) National Energy Agreement for sustainable growth. The goal of this agreement was to make Dutch energy supply more sustainable. The Energy Agreement contains policies extending until 2020/2023 as a step towards an 80 to 95% GHG reduction in 2050. The 47 signatories agreed on an average yearly final energy consumption reduction of 1.5% and 100 PJ final energy consumption reduction in 2020. The target set for the contribution of renewable energy was 14% in 2020 and 16% in 2023. To realize the target of 16%, the agreement states that a mix of mainly decentralized sustainable energy options must be considered. It explicitly mentions that the majority of the generating capacity from decentralized sustainable energy should come from bioenergy systems such as bio-CHP⁶.

The National Energy Agreement was succeeded by the Climate Agreement in 2019, which put the emphasis on GHG-emission reduction targets instead of renewable energy targets. The Climate Agreement has set a GHG-emission reduction target of 49% in 2030 and 95% in 2050 with respect to 1990 levels⁷. This target is laid down in the Climate Act. The Dutch House of Representatives aimed to realize a cost-effective energy transition, and therefore, did not advocate a specific technology. They rather remained “technology neutral” challenging innovators to come up with the best solutions. The Climate Agreement highlighted biomass and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) as a cost-effective way of realizing the targets and can be considered an intermediate solution before e.g., electrification of the energy system could be realized.

In 2019, the NGO Mobilisation for the Environment (MOB) successfully challenged the permitting system concerning nitrogen emissions (Programma Aanpak Stikstof), causing 18,000 building and infrastructural projects to be halted. To resolve this “nitrogen crisis” a State Advisory Board (Commission-Remkes) published an advice titled “Not everything is possible everywhere”⁸. While the impact of biomass boilers in the range of 0.5 – 50 MW is estimated to be of minor relevance (0.02 – 0.06% of total deposition on Nature 2000 areas)⁹, the report

⁶<https://www.ser.nl/nl/thema/energie-en-duurzaamheid/energieakkoord/-/media/5A6DE312EAB948BEADF43DECF2DF5669.ashx>

⁷ Klimaatakkoord, 28 juni 2019

⁸ REMkes et al (2020) Niet alles kan Overal, Eindadvies of structurele aanpak adviescollege Stikstofproblematiek, <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/rapporten/2020/06/08/niet-alles-kan-overal>

⁹ <https://www.stichtingbeon.nl/stikstofuitstoot-biomassacentrales-lager-dan-verondersteld/>

advised the state to tighten emission limits and to end the eligibility for renewable energy production subsidies (SDE+) for these installations.

Given the criticism on bioenergy on the one hand and the need for bioenergy to meet renewable energy and climate goals, the Dutch House of Representatives stipulated the development of framework conditions for sustainable biomass. The first step in this process was to draw up a report concerning the availability of all types of biomass, considering the fair-share principle and sustainability levels, and giving a view on the potential applications for sustainable biomass, taking cascading use of biomass as starting point¹⁰. The results served as input for a formal advice from the Dutch Social Economic Council (SER) "*Biomass in balance, sustainability framework for optimal utilisation of biomass feedstocks*"¹¹. It states that the use of biomass for high temperature heat, like steam production is regarded as a "bridging application" for the next years, and that low temperature heating using biomass should be phased out, gradually replaced by alternatives, such as geothermal and heat pumps. In the long run, biomass should be deployed in high-value applications, such as bio-based chemicals and bio-based materials¹².

Currently, bio-CHP is being promoted through the Sustainable Energy Production Incentive Scheme (SDE++), which supports renewable electricity, gas and heat production by means of a feed-in-premium which is equal to the difference between a base rate and a correction rate, determined retroactively every year for certain technologies. The scheme allows all technologies to compete against each other rather than pre-allocating a certain share of the budget for each technology.

After the resignation of the Dutch government on 15 January 2021, bioenergy subsidies for woody biomass have been regarded controversial, as the phase out of bioenergy for low temperature heating has not been sufficiently elaborated¹³. This means that if no new government is formed before September 2021, new woody bioenergy projects may not be eligible for SDE++ subsidy in 2021. In 2022 it appeared that new bioenergy installations will only subsidised if they deliver heat/steam of at least 100°C¹⁴.

Media analysis

A total of 299 articles were retrieved from the Nexis Newsdesk database. Of these 299 articles, 174 articles were found most relevant to the subject, and will be used as proxy to assess social acceptance of bioenergy in The Netherlands.

Bioenergy (in this case, energy from woody biomass) has been a subject of discussion ever since bioenergy was integrated in the first Dutch National Energy Agreement. It was considered both a carbon-neutral option to produce energy and an effective way of substituting coal in coal-fired power stations. Bioenergy received considerably more media attention from mid-2017 onwards. Partly, the increasing number of articles discussing bioenergy is a consequence of the fact that there were an increasing number of events to report. Figure 3-1 depicts the sentiment of each article and relates this to specific 'trigger events', such as the release of a scientific report, the broadcast of a documentary, or a milestone in the

¹⁰ Klimaatplan 2021-2030, Ministerie van Economische Zaken en Klimaat

¹¹ Biomassa in balans: Een duurzaamheidskader voor hoogwaardige inzet van biogrondstoffen; Sociaal-Economische Raad, Juli 2020

¹² <https://www.ser.nl/nl/Publicaties/waarde-halen-uit-biomassa>

¹³ Gewijzigde motie 30175 nr. 372 van het lid Van Esch c.s. over geen nieuwe subsidies voor houtige biomassa (t.v.v. 30175-360) <https://www.tweedekamer.nl/kamerstukken/moties/detail?id=2021Z03880&did=2021D08416>

¹⁴ https://www.rvo.nl/sites/default/files/2022-05/Brochure_SDE_plus-plus-2022.pdf

development or implementation of a bioenergy production plant. In general, bioenergy received predominantly positive attention in the beginning of 2017, however the sentiment radically changed from 2018 onwards. The Dutch newspapers were mostly negative from the end of 2020 until mid-2021, whereby newspaper articles with positive sentiments were only minor rebuttals from a few bioenergy proponents.

It must be noted that although the media analysis was conducted from 2017 until mid-2021, biomass was already a subject of discussion in the Netherlands. Case in point, a few signees of the Energy Agreement (e.g., Greenpeace, Milieudefensie, and Natuur & Milieu) reluctantly agreed on the use of biomass as renewable energy source. Their motivation to agree on the use of biomass was the phasing-out of coal use in the five coal-fired power stations, as these could be fully retrofitted into biomass-fired power stations. In 2015, the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (KNAW) has published a "Vision Document biofuels and wood as energy sources"¹⁵ in which it was claimed that co-combustion of wood for electricity production and biofuels for transport are ineffective ways to reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases.

2017-2018

In 2017, bioenergy was mentioned in relation to the election of the Dutch Parliament. Surprisingly, climate change was barely mentioned in each of the political parties' programs or even during political debates. During the elections, an open letter was sent by 90 professors, addressed to the future cabinet, in which twelve recommendations were drafted concerning the transition to the bioeconomy. These professors argued for the immediate shut-down of the remaining five coal-fired power stations, but specifically disapproved the conversion to biomass-fired power stations. They argued that "*the conversion required too much subsidy and too little CO₂-reduction*".¹⁶

The discussion on bioenergy was further stimulated when the energy company RWE announced plans to co-fire 30% biomass in its coal-fired power plant. According to climate organizations Greenpeace, Natuur & Milieu, and Milieudefensie, RWE did not procure sustainably sourced wood (e.g., FSC-labelled wood), which was the main pre-condition for them signing the first National Energy Agreement. The announcement from RWE triggered a fair amount of media attention and instigated a second wave of articles with a negative sentiment. The Dutch media referred to Timothy Searchinger's conclusion back in 2008, stating that the climate neutral classification for bioenergy is a calculation error¹⁷. At this point, the print media seeds more disbelief about the sustainability of woody biomass for energy purposes and is even labelled as "climate killer" by publisher Trouw.

¹⁵ KNAW (2015) Visiedocument biobrandstof en hout als energiebronnen, effect op uitstoot van broeikasgassen

¹⁶ <https://www.trouw.nl/nieuws/hoogleraren-alles-op-alles-zetten-voor-groene-economie~b9549bda/>

¹⁷ <https://www.trouw.nl/nieuws/waarom-biomassa-een-grotere-klimaatkiller-is-dan-steenkool~b8d089d1/>

Figure 3-1: The number of articles concerning bioenergy published in Dutch newspapers in the period 2017-2021, subdivided in positive, neutral, and negative articles including related key 'trigger events'. DHoR: Dutch House of Representatives

2018-2019

During late 2017 and practically the entirety of 2018, the media attention for bioenergy was mainly related to the Climate Agreement negotiations. In this period, the majority of the news articles had a negative sentiment. As for the National Energy Agreement, the shut-down of the remaining coal-fired power plants was discussed during the Climate Agreement negotiations. At first, the media emphasized the previous negotiations in which the climate organizations reluctantly agreed on biomass co-firing. The print media made it clear that this agreement was a one-time concession to swiftly shut-down the coal-fired power stations (Greenpeace: "We are not willing to negotiate about biomass co-firing")¹⁸. Subsequently, newspapers became increasingly sceptic regarding biomass as energy source. In particular, the amount of subsidy required for biomass co-firing and the credibility of the carbon-accounting system (e.g., carbon cycle) were questioned. More specifically, an opinion article in De Volkskrant labelled the carbon-accounting system as "fraudulent trick"¹⁹.

Within the same period, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) published an article on mitigation pathways that are consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels²⁰. Biomass is one of the prominent pathways according to the report. This conclusion from the IPCC gained little attention within the Dutch print media. At the end of 2018, the way bioenergy was

¹⁸ Energie uit biomassa is niet zaligmakend; Algemeen Dagblad, 15 Dec. 2017.

¹⁹ <https://www.volkskrant.nl/columns-opinie/beperk-co2-door-betere-benutting-van-biosystemen~be95de12/>

²⁰ https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/sites/2/2019/02/SR15_Chapter2_Low_Res.pdf

covered by the media was almost completely shifted to negative as opposed to 2017.

2019-2020

The increase in negative sentiment continued with the media coverage of the Dutch environmental assessment agency (Planbureau voor de Leefomgeving – PBL) being responsible for the quantitative impact assessment of the Climate agreement. The media made negative statements regarding PBL. Several media defined PBL as “green activists” and “subjective” when it comes to bioenergy (Quote: “*Their task is to reveal the facts, not to follow the political defined rules*”)²¹. The end of 2019 saw a peak in bioenergy related news articles, which was a consequence of the European Academies Science Advisory Council’s (EASAC) conclusions on bioenergy and the letters from the Area Health Authority (Gemeentelijke Geneeskundige Dienst – GGD) to the ministry of Climate and Economic Affairs. These events were covered quite extensively by the print media and were predominantly negative in sentiment.

Only now, the Dutch media brought the conclusions from EASAC to the attention, while their report was published in 2017²² and subsequently re-emphasized in a press release in 2018²³. EASAC argued that carbon emissions per unit of electricity generated from forest biomass are higher than from coal. This particular statement was already used in the media at this point, but now became a reference and ultimately the norm for any forthcoming news article. The letter from the GGD was intended to warn the ministry of Climate and Economic Affairs about the negative health consequences of the emissions of biomass plants. According to the GGD, biomass combustion to produce energy results in an increase in the concentration of particulate matter. Major concerns were raised in the Dutch Newspapers. At the same time, Commission-Remkes, appointed to address the nitrogen-crisis, broadened their initial scope beyond the agricultural sector to also include the energy sector. One of their conclusions was to stop the subsidies for small-scale biomass plants due to the increased nitrogen deposits in several Natura 2000 areas. The media took the opportunity to spread the word and thereby succeeded to characterize biomass as health and environmental risk. *Algemeen Dagblad* published a news article with the headline “Biomass is not sustainable, but rather kills people”.

2020-2021

In 2020, news articles were dominated by the release of Michael Moore’s documentary called “Planet of the Humans”. In this documentary, countless sustainable dogmas were rejected of which biomass was one of them. Many articles were dedicated to this documentary and agreed with Michael Moore to reject biomass as sustainable source. Furthermore, the reports of PBL (i.e., “Biomass in

²¹ <https://www.telegraaf.nl/nieuws/3190408/rekenen-is-politiek-voor-groen-planbureau-voor-de-leefomgeving>

²² <https://easac.eu/publications/details/multi-functionality-and-sustainability-in-the-european-unions-forests/>

²³ https://easac.eu/fileadmin/PDF_s/reports_statements/Carbon_Neutrality/EASAC_Press_Release_on_Carbon_Neutrality_15_June_2018.pdf

perspective”) and SER (i.e., “*Biomass in balance, sustainability framework for optimal utilisation of biomass feedstocks*”) were frequently mentioned. These reports have been drafted as requested by the council of ministers due to the strong polarization of the biomass debate. According to PBL “*Every argument is legit in its own right*”. In other words, everyone involved in the biomass discussion is right in its own perspective. Many bioenergy opponents expressed their dissatisfaction and rather saw a definitive conclusion that would halt bioenergy production from woody biomass. Later, in contrast to the PBL report, the SER report recommended to stop the subsidies for biomass that serve the energy production. Newspapers called it a “breakthrough in the BIO-discussion”. Within this year, the biomass discussion was so overheated that the consumer decided to deliberately avoid energy contracts in which biomass was part of the green energy source²⁴.

2021

During the 2021 election of the Dutch House of Representatives, climate change was a major topic. Yet, bioenergy only came to the attention by the media due to the position of GroenLinks towards bioenergy. The leader of this political party expressed himself negatively about bioenergy while they approved the construction of most of the bioenergy plants in the past 4 years. Also, more and more political parties expressed their concerns regarding bioenergy and rather see an end to the subsidies for any new bioenergy plant.

In all newspapers, risks (negative SPEED framing) were mentioned more often than benefits (positive SPEED framing) when discussing bioenergy (see Figure 3-2). To be exact, 69% of all articles had a negative sentiment while only 13% were positive. Risks were mentioned more than benefits for the technological, health &

Figure 3-2: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 174 articles assessed in the Dutch media from 2017 to 2021

²⁴ <https://www.telegraaf.nl/financieel/1985596301/ook-consument-is-biomassa-nu-beu>

safety, environmental, economic, and cultural SPEED frames, while benefits are mentioned more often only in the political SPEED frame. Health & safety and especially environmental frames dominate the bioenergy discourse while the technical and cultural frames were largely absent.

The reason that the cultural frame is almost absent in public discourse is that bioenergy production does not interfere with our daily lives and therefore no behavioral change is required, and privacy risks are non-existent. This is, for example, different from media analysis of other emerging technologies like smart grid. Strikingly, the Dutch print media portrayed bioenergy as environmental and economic risk while bioenergy is defined as sustainable by the EU and should even strengthen the economy by creating additional jobs. Table 3-1 shows the positive and negative statements used within each SPEED frame and gives an indication to how this observation came about. Clearly, the major themes in the news articles are the *disbelieve* of biomass being sustainable, the *effects* of biomass cultivation for energy (i.e., deforestation and decline in biodiversity) and the *concerns* about human health and air quality. Essentially, the disbelieve of biomass being sustainable concerns the credibility of the carbon-accounting system. In general, three main arguments are repetitively used which discredits the system. Firstly, biomass combustion is less efficient than fossil fuels as it contains a certain

Table 3-1: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Dutch news articles on bioenergy.

Positive statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Biomass is necessary to reach our climate goals	14	44%
2. Unlike wind- and solar energy, biomass can be constantly produced	5	16%
3. Biomass is climate-neutral	4	13%
4. Biomass is necessary to reduce CO ₂ -emissions	2	6%
5. Biomass for energy results in a significant CO ₂ -reduction	2	6%
6. Biomass can be sustainable when it comes from sustainable forests	2	6%

Negative statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Bioenergy is even more dirty than any other form of fossil energy	47	33%
2. Biomass for energy purposes leads to deforestation	27	19%
3. Biomass for energy purposes causes a decline in biodiversity	14	10%
4. Biomass combustion is bad for human health	11	8%
5. Biomass is not sustainable	10	7%
6. Biomass combustion is bad for the air quality	6	4%
7. Biomass combustion is damaging the environment	4	3%
8. Biomass costs billions in subsidies	3	2%
9. Biomass is not carbon-neutral	3	2%
10. Subsidies costs taxpayers a lot of money	2	1%

percentage of moisture. Secondly, it takes approximately 20 years for a tree to capture the same amount of carbon emitted during combustion. Lastly, the same trees being cut down cannot capture CO₂ anymore, which result in increased levels of CO₂. Several scientific reports and press releases confirms that biomass is a bigger emitter than other fossil fuels, such as those reports from Timothy Searchinger, KNAW and EASAC. On the other hand, when it comes to the concern of deforestation as a consequence of bioenergy production, the media never supported such statement with scientific reports, however, was only based on interviews with forestry experts and environmental organizations. Yet, it is one of the main arguments used against bioenergy. The concern of human health and the air quality came about after the announcement of the letter from the GGD to the ministry of Climate and Economic Affairs and the report from commission-Remkes, respectively.

Ultimately, the presence of bioenergy skeptics in the media was dominant, backed-up by a handful of scientific reports and press releases. Remarkably, those reports that did not had a pronounced negative position regarding bioenergy (i.e., IPCC and PBL), received little attention or were immediately discredited. Of the 174 assessed articles, only a handful argued against the bioenergy skeptics. Their prime argument during the biomass debate was to continue the production of bioenergy as it was required to reach their climate goals.

The Dutch media played a pivotal role in the social acceptance of bioenergy. This was confirmed when CBS published their results of a survey regarding the citizens' perception of climate change and the energy transition. Wind- and solar energy, geothermal energy, and hydropower received positive feedback. The opinion on biomass in particular was rather divided²⁵.

3.1.2 Sweden

Policy analysis

²⁵ <https://www.cbs.nl/nl-nl/longread/rapportages/2021/klimateverandering-en-energietransitie-opvattingen-en-gedrag-van-nederlanders-in-2020/3-opvattingen-over-energietransitie>

In Sweden, bioenergy has been supported by local and government policies since the oil crisis in 1973 and 1979. These events became the starting point for Swedish energy policy in a broader sense, which led to the adoption of energy security and reduced oil consumption as overall policy objectives during the 1970s and 80s. Their strategy relied on energy conservation and the development and increased use of domestic energy resources such as biomass. Subsequently, government spending on energy research, development and demonstration (RD&D) was considerably increased. RD&D in bioenergy was one of the priorities which included fuels from forestry residues, short rotation forestry, fuel refinement and conversion technology²⁶. Within the same period, the use of biomass for heat production was stimulated through investment subsidies for construction of demonstration plants burning solid fuels²⁷. Additionally, the use of biomass, amongst others, was further promoted through the Solid Fuel Act, which obliged the adaptation of new boilers to be able to burn solid fuels²⁸.

As biomass was not an obvious choice of energy source in the district heating sector from an economic point of view, strong local commitment often played an important role in the deployment of biomass co-fired CHP plants. One example is the town of Borås where the municipal council decided to co-fire biomass with coal as a substitute for fuel oil in a CHP plant in the early 1980s, despite the opposition from the municipal energy administration management who advocated coal only (Jacobsson, 2008).

The issue of climate change came into view by Swedish politics around 1990 and has since then been an important factor in energy policy and a driver for bioenergy¹¹. At that point, Sweden amended the energy taxation which instituted a carbon tax. The energy taxes formerly did not stimulate the use of biomass until the amendment thereof in 1991. The energy and carbon taxes are levied on fuels used in heat production, but not on those used in electricity production. At first, the carbon tax was set at 25 €/ton CO₂, which gradually increased to 112 €/ton CO₂ in 2015. Consequently, the cost of coal in district heat production immediately doubled and biomass became the cheapest fuel in this application. Yet, this tax was conducive to a large-scale diffusion of biomass in district heating but not to power production. Due to a powerful external blocking mechanism in the form of low power prices and a set of important external inducement mechanisms that involved a destabilization of the energy sector (i.e., dismantling of nuclear power), bioenergy opportunities rose significantly (Raven, 2005). In fact, a commission that was appointed to assess the opportunities for bioenergy production found these to be substantial and it was even suggested that support should be given primarily to CHP production using biomass²⁹. What followed was two governmental investment grant schemes (in 1992-1997 and 1997-2002) which played a key role in the market formation of biomass-based CHP in Sweden (Jacobsson, 2008).

In 2003, the investment grants schemes supporting the production of renewable electricity were replaced by a scheme for Tradable Renewable Electricity Certificates (TREC)s, whereby suppliers of 'green electricity', including bioenergy, were given a green certificate for each MWh they supplied to the net. These green

²⁶ The Use of Biomass for Energy in Sweden – Critical Factors and Lessons Learned; Bengt Johansson, et al. 2002.

²⁷ Bioenergi från jordbruket - en växande resurs [Bioenergy from agriculture - A growing resource]; Statens offentliga utredningar SOU, 2007.

²⁸ Lag Om Utförande Av Eldningsanläggningar För Fastbränsle (Avslutad I SFS 1994:793) [Act for design of heating plants for solid fuels (terminated in SFS 1994:793)]; Swedish Parliament, 1981

²⁹ SOU, 1991:93. El från biobränsle. Delbetänkande av biobränslekommissionen, Stockholm

certificates are then bought by power users who are obliged to fulfil a certain quota of 'green power'. The sales of these certificates generate additional income to the producer of renewable electricity apart from the electricity sold. The scheme has provided a strong economic incentive for biomass-based CHP production and has led to considerable investments in new biomass-fired CHP plants (Jacobsson, 2008). The scheme was initially limited to the period 2003-2010 but has been extended until 2035³⁰.

Media analysis

A total of 184 articles were retrieved from Dagens Nyheter. Of these 184 articles, 69 articles were found most relevant to the subject, and will be used as proxy to assess social acceptance of bioenergy in Sweden.

Figure 3-3: The number of articles concerning bioenergy published in the Swedish newspaper Dagens Nyheter in the period 2017-2021, subdivided in positive, neutral, and negative articles including related key 'trigger events'.

2017-2018

In early and mid-2017, bioenergy was framed by the media as a sustainable practice that contributes significantly to meeting the climate goals for 2030. This was evidenced by the Royal Swedish Academy of Engineering Sciences (ICU) in their report "Samhällsbyggande, drivmedel och energi" (translation: Community building, fuel and energy)³¹. They found that more wooden houses and greater investments in bioenergy could help solving some major societal challenges, and therefore, makes the Swedish forest an important player in the work towards a greener society. The first critique towards bioenergy (at least in the assessed period) came about the time the EASAC published their report "multi-functionality and sustainability in the European Union's forests". One publisher echoed some of

³⁰ <http://www.energimyndigheten.se/fornybart/elcertifikatsystemet/om-elcertifikatsystemet/>

³¹ <https://www.iva.se/publicerat/samhallsbyggande-drivmedel-och-energi--en-delrapport/>

the findings of the EASAC report, like the fact that the so-called repayment period is a critical factor in the use of bioenergy (i.e., 10-20 years for residues and about 100 years for stem wood), and that increased felling would drastically reduce the net carbon sink. Instead, increasing carbon storage in existing forests would be a very cost-effective way of reducing net GHG emissions to the atmosphere, as stated in the article. These statements in the print media evoked a discussion in which multiple stakeholders refuted the aforementioned statements. According to them, the conclusions that were drawn lacked system vision, quote: “the role of forests cannot be valued on the basis of narrow reflections of carbon flows within individual forest stocks”.

2018-2019

In early 2018, EASAC released their report “Negative emission technologies: What role in meeting Paris Agreement targets?” stating that none of the negative emission technologies (NETs) has the potential to deliver carbon removals at the gigaton scale and at the rate of deployment envisaged by the IPCC.³² According to the IPCC, a fifth of the global carbon budget has already been released in the last 5 years. Negative emissions are needed to keep the carbon budget, but unless the pace of reducing our direct emissions increases, it will not be enough. Thus, as one of the news articles states, “it does not indicate that the techniques should not be applied”. According to the media, one of the key NETs for Sweden is Bioenergy Carbon Capture & Storage (BECCS), whereby the captured biogenic CO₂ from biomass combustion can be stored in bedrock. Throughout 2018, multiple articles appeared concerning the deployment of BECCS as potential technology that could help to retain the carbon budget, thereby realising the targets set in the Paris agreement. The IPCC report published in late 2018 confirmed the need for NETs as the carbon budget will exceed within 10 years with today’s emission levels.³³ This release of the IPCC report was followed by a few news articles stressing the potential and urge of BECCS deployment in Sweden.

2019-2020

In late 2018 and early 2019, the sustainability of biofuels and bioenergy were being criticized by researchers Timothy D. Searchinger and Stefan Wirsenius, as well as the youth movement led by Greta Thunberg, claiming that it stands in the way of establishing forest that can bind CO₂, and causes deforestation as well. The researchers argue that in the short term, the future uptake of CO₂ by forests is of no use as a felled surface does not absorb any CO₂ for the first 10-15 years. Only after 60-120 years will the forest compensate for the emissions that have occurred in the first years after felling. This opinion article was followed by multiple articles claiming that their conclusions run counter to both the IPCC report and the Royal Swedish Academy of Forestry and Agriculture report. According to the debaters, the uptake of CO₂ in forests and land must be considered in a long-term perspective. In addition, they argue that it is more of a climate benefit to harvest forests than to leave the trees standing and aging, as the degree of CO₂ adsorption declines as trees are aging.

2020-2021

In January 2020, the Swedish Ministry of Environment released a report entitled “The Pathway to a Climate Positive Future”. This report presented the findings of a public committee tasked with investigating opportunities for achieving negative

³² https://easac.eu/publications/details/easac_net/

³³ https://www.ipcc.ch/site/assets/uploads/sites/2/2019/02/SR15_Chapter2_Low_Res.pdf

GHG emissions as part of Sweden’s long-term climate change mitigation target. By exploring different ways to develop NETs, the report provided a first attempt to visualise a future in which the country eventually removes more carbon from the atmosphere than it emits. Multiple opinion articles stressed the urge to not only reduce emissions, but also to capture the CO₂ already in the atmosphere. It is recognized that BECCS could play a key role.

2021

The discussion around the sustainability of bioenergy took flight late 2020 and early 2021 after Dagens Nyheter shed light on multiple violations on the environmental certification rules (i.e., FSC) by forest companies in their review series on Swedish forestry. One such example is that Sveaskog failed to preserve forests carrying high natural value (i.e., preservation of key biotopes), which is a condition for both FSC and PEFC certification³⁴. Furthermore, the discussion was fed even further due to the negotiations on the EU’s new climate policy (i.e., Taxonomy) in which Sweden played a key role. The initial proposal of the taxonomy regulation described bioenergy as “a transitional solution”. The Swedish government worked actively to avoid bioenergy to be seen as a transitional solution. For instance, Energy Minister Anders Ygeman appealed to the responsible EU commissioner to continue to count forest biofuels as sustainable, and Prime Minister Stefan Löfven appealed in a meeting with the President of the European Commission for “understanding and respect for Swedish sustainable forestry”. Multiple opinion articles appeared as a reaction to Swedish’s role in the negotiations of the Taxonomy. On the one hand, the writers expressed the fact that sustainable bioenergy is important in Sweden’s ambition to increase renewables and to phase out fossil energy, and on the other hand, writers state that the production interests in the forest take precedence over environmental considerations.

In all articles, risks (negative SPEED framing) were marginally more often mentioned than benefits (positive SPEED framing) when discussing bioenergy. To be exact, 55% of all articles had a negative sentiment while 45% were positive. Risks were mentioned slightly more often than benefits for the environmental SPEED frame, while benefits are mentioned slightly more often in the political SPEED frame. Especially, the environmental frame dominated the bioenergy discourse while the technical, health & safety, cultural, and economic frames were largely absent.

³⁴ <https://www.sverigesnatur.org/aktuellt/ovantat-samarbete-kan-radda-renbetet/>

Figure 3-4: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 69 articles assessed in the Swedish media from 2017 to 2021.

The reason that the cultural frame is almost absent in public discourse is that bioenergy production does not interfere with our daily lives and therefore no behavioral change is required, and privacy risks are non-existent. Notably, the health & safety frame is almost completely absent in Swedish media, while this was a prominent frame in the Dutch media. Table 3-2 shows the positive and negative statements used within each SPEED frame and gives an indication to how this observation came about. By looking at the sheer number of statements, it is not possible to distinguish between major themes. However, taking into account the content and course of the discussion, it became clear that the media was quite divided and that two “camps” can be differentiated. The dividing line is between those who wants to conduct more forestry, and those who wants to preserve more forest. The major difference between these two camps is the timescale. Bioenergy opponents believe that it takes between 40-150 years for planted trees to capture as much carbon dioxide as has been emitted during a felling. This is good from a long-term perspective, however, we have to halve the emissions in just 10 years to reach the Paris Agreement. Bioenergy proponents state that the carbon from bioenergy is part of the “green cycle” with a shorter orbital period and is expected to be absorbed by new growing trees. In this way, that carbon does not contribute to the increase in carbon dioxide in the atmosphere.

Despite the critique, bioenergy is expected to play a key role as Sweden has committed itself to achieve GHG emissions with BECCS as prominent technology.

Table 3-2: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Swedish news articles on bioenergy.

Positive statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Bioenergy is climate neutral	4	13.3%
2. Leaving the forest untouched will risk completely missing the climate targets	3	10%
3. Bioenergy can contribute to achieve the climate goals	2	6.6%
4. Bioenergy needs to increase in order to achieve the climate goals	2	6.6%
5. Active forestry is important for the Swedish economy, growth, and jobs	1	3.3%
6. It is possible to use forests efficiently and still achieve sustainability	1	3.3%
Negative statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Bioenergy is even more dirty than any other form of fossil energy	8	20%
2. Bioenergy is not climate neutral	6	15.8%
3. Bioenergy drives biodiversity loss	6	15.8%
4. The uptake of carbon dioxide takes too long to reach the climate targets	4	10.5%
5. Accounting rules and economic instruments created an industry that further reduces our changes of achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement	2	5.3%
6. Bioenergy causes forest degradation/deforestation	2	5.3%

3.1.3 Croatia

Policy analysis

Following EU requirements, Croatia adopted a National Action Plan for Renewable Energy Sources (Action Plan) back in 2013, as the implementing instrument for the realization of EU targets and national energy strategy up to 2020. The overall national target for the share of energy from renewable energy sources (RES) in the gross final consumption of energy is 20%. The National Action Plan specifically targets three sectors. One of which is the electricity sector which has a sectoral objective of achieving a 35% share of RES. Biomass is perceived as a dominant renewable source to reach the 35% share of RES with a planned contribution of 26 PJ and 85 MW of capacity in 2020.

Furthermore, the Action Plan implemented a support scheme to encourage the use of CHP from renewable energy sources via already existing policies. The legal framework for the promotion of the use of cogeneration for electricity production was adopted in 2007 (i.e., Energy Act (official Gazette 120/12) Electricity Market Act (Official Gazette 22/13)). All market participants and their roles in the electricity market in Croatia are explained in accordance with these energy legislations. A power producer in Croatia is classified either as an eligible producer or an independent producer. An eligible producer is a producer with both grid and market

priority. RES/CHP generators may obtain a so-called “eligibility status”. All RES/CHP generators that attain this status are subsidized under the Feed-in-Tariff (FiT) support scheme. According to the tariff system, the Croatian Electricity Market Operator (HROTE) is obliged to off-take electricity from eligible producers at a fixed price on the basis of a 14-year contract. This guarantees long-term security for a certain producer³⁵.

In 2016, a new act on renewable energy sources and high-efficiency cogeneration came into force, which provided a framework for supporting RES and CHP electricity production via market premium contracts obtained through a bidding process. RES under a market premium system will be able to sell electricity according to the same market principles as any other conventional producer. The only difference is that RES additionally receives a premium from HROTE, which is the difference between the reference cost for each RES technology and the market price (Beus, Pavić, Štritof, Capuder, & Pandžić, 2018).

Loans and subsidies for renewable energy projects are also provided. The loans granted for the implementation of renewable energy projects are part of the “environmental protection” loan scheme by the Croatian Bank for Reconstruction and Development (HBOR). In addition, the Environmental Protection and Energy Efficiency Fund (FZOEU) offers financial incentives (interest-free loans, subsidies, etc.) for the use of renewable energy sources³⁶.

Media analysis

The assessment of selected Croatian Newspapers (Jutarni list, Vecernji list, 24sata) resulted in 27 articles in which the search term “biomass” was used in the context of bioenergy. Articles cover 2018 – 2022. The main findings are discussed below.

One third (9 out of the 27)^{37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45}, of the news articles cover announcements of investments, construction or realisation of specific bioenergy plants, mainly wood chips fired CHP plants. In these articles the mayor or the investor typically emphasise the employment and economic benefits for the region. Part of these online articles received negative comments about forests that would

³⁵ Croatian National Renewable Energy Action Plan, 2013

³⁶<http://www.res-legal.eu/search-by-country/croatia/tools-list/c/croatia/s/res-e/t/promotion/sum/358/lpid/359/>

³⁷ <https://www.jutarnji.hr/globus/biznis/babina-greda-upisala-se-na-kartu-uspjesnih-investicija-kako-radi-najjaca-hrvatska-elektrana-na-drvnu-sjecku-6900015>

³⁸ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/makro-mikro/vukovarsko-kogeneracijsko-postrojenje-enna-grupe-bit-ce-dovrseno-do-kraja-listopada-7742895>

³⁹ <https://www.vecernji.hr/vijesti/elektricna-energija-iz-biomase-pocet-ce-se-proizvoditi-u-studenom-1265208>

⁴⁰ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/makro-mikro/u-kogeneracijsko-postrojenje-reneteh-u-ogulinu-slovacki-vlasnici-ulozili-150-milijuna-kn-8121014>

⁴¹ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/makro-mikro/norvezani-u-karlovcu-investirali-15-mil-pokrecu-toplanu-na-biomasi-i-proizvodnju-peleta-8725544>

⁴² https://www.google.com/url?client=internal-element-cse&cx=partner-pub-6170662397256706:s0xfwxcxobj&q=https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/ceski-energetski-holding-ulozio-80-milijuna-eura-u-hrvatskoj-i-sprema-novu-investiciju-9917734&sa=U&ved=2ahUKEwiTvNK0jaD3AhVESPEDHXzACCwQFnoECAcQAg&usg=AOvVaw0jfvuYGVl5Ll_-3CyPS8Jr

⁴³ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/veliki-projekt-ina-e-u-sisku-250-milijuna-eura-za-gradnju-biorafinerije-10415659>

⁴⁴ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/makro-mikro/usred-like-investicija-vrijedna-preko-20-milijuna-eura-15025387>

⁴⁵ <https://www.vecernji.hr/biznis/u-gospicu-s-radom-zapocela-energana-od-20-milijuna-eura-evo-koliko-ce-ljudi-zaposljavati-1505045>

need to be cut and air pollution that could be caused by these installations, but the main article does not address these concerns.

Eight articles^{46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53} had a conference, project presentation or report as trigger event. Topics include high export of wood pellets/low development of domestic pellet market, the possibilities of agro pellets, the potential of forest biomass or agricultural residues, and the planning of a national plan for the use of biomass in the public sector. In general, these articles are positive about technical, economic, and environmental benefits of bioenergy, and on reaching renewable energy targets (political benefit). The publication of the JRC study *"The use of woody biomass for energy production in the EU"*⁵⁴ was the trigger for one article⁵¹ with a strong negative heading: *"Combustion of forest biomass produces more greenhouse gases than coal, oil and gas"*. As a reaction a commentary article *"Biomass will always play a significant role in energy"*, was placed in which Professor Neven Duić explains that this sensationalist article sets out views not found in the JRC's report, providing further explanation of the principle of cascading and the need to reduce biodiversity impacts. After this article the discussion ended.

Besides the above, number of articles covering risks of biomass for energy are rather limited. One article⁵⁵ describes the reaction of Finland on the leaked draft EU forestry strategy in 2021, discussing that forest must not become "wood farms". One article addressed air quality mentioning biomass furnaces next to other causes like transport emissions, but no call for action was made to make air quality better, in this article⁵⁶ titled *"I'm worried about poor air quality, but it happens all the time"*. One article - not containing the term biomass and without a reference to bioenergy and thus not analysed in the SPEED analysis - reports on the clear cut of thousands of trees near the city of Borovik (Slavonia), located on a popular and important hiking trail. However, the article emphasises that in order to rejuvenate the stands logging is prescribed by the management program approved by the Ministry of Agriculture. In an additional box under the article Professor of agroforestry Vladimir Ivezic explains that *"It's not nice to see, but it doesn't mean that forestry is not sustainable"*.

⁴⁶ <https://www.vecernji.hr/biznis/peleti-oie-konferencija-biomasa-davor-skrlec-tomislav-coric-1229256>

⁴⁷ <https://www.jutarnji.hr/globus/biznis/velika-prednost-obnovljivih-izvora-energije-ako-se-ubrzanjihova-primjena-godisnje-bi-se-moglo-ustedjeti-izmedu-52-i-133-milijarde-eura-do-2030-7100265>

⁴⁸ <https://www.vecernji.hr/biznis/spas-za-poljoprivredu-buducnost-slavonije-agropeleti-zelena-energija-1231593>

⁴⁹ <https://www.24sata.hr/news/rados-hrvatskoj-je-potrebna-nova-energetska-strategija-571281>

⁵⁰ <https://www.vecernji.hr/biznis/pandemija-dodatno-uzdrmla-pilarski-sektor-skladista-punacijene-dampinske-1434089>

⁵¹ <https://www.jutarnji.hr/planet/izgaranjem-sumske-biomase-proizvodi-se-vise-staklenickih-plinova-nego-u-slucaju-ugljena-nafte-i-plina-15048928>

⁵² <https://www.jutarnji.hr/planet/petir-hrvatska-ima-jedan-od-najvecih-potencijala-u-eu-za-razvoj-biogospodarstva-15065990>

⁵³ <https://novac.jutarnji.hr/novac/rasprave-i-rjesenja/biomasa-ce-uvijek-imati-znacajnu-ulogu-u-energetici-15055019>

⁵⁴ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7120db75-6118-11eb-8146-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁵⁵ <https://www.jutarnji.hr/planet/finsko-drustvo-pred-sukobom-zastiti-sume-ili-ih-upotrijebiti-kao-materijal-za-nadomjestak-nafte-15099744>

⁵⁶ <https://www.24sata.hr/news/zabrinut-sam-za-losu-kvalitetu-zraka-ali-to-se-stalno-dogada-670707>

Some articles highlight the consumers' view pointing to an available investment subsidy for pellet boilers⁵⁷, or refer to pellet boilers as a way to avoid high fossil energy prices⁵⁸.

Analysis of the 27 articles on biomass resulted in 45 statements, of which 7 addressed risks, 29 covered benefits and 9 were neutral statements. Figure 3-5 and Table 3-3 show that the economic benefits (especially on employment) are mentioned in 13 out of 45 statements (29%). Political benefits (targets) and technical benefits (flexibility, advantages of certain boiler types) are found in 9 and 4 statements, respectively. Only in the environmental SPEED frame the risks dominate with 5 statements, which were related to international trigger events, such as the JRC study on the use of woody biomass for energy production in the EU (3 statements) and the Finish reaction on the leaked EU forestry strategy (2 statements). Health and safety risks were related to an accident with a circular saw during construction of a biomass boiler and a period with bad air quality. The single statement on cultural benefits was about strengthening social cohesion resulting from the employment and income generated from a new biomass boiler.

Neutral statements include technical facts and investment costs of biomass boilers, an explanation of cascading use, numbers of applications for pellet subsidies, and the announcement of a national plan for use of biomass in the public sector.

In general, the topic of bioenergy is covered in the media in a rather positive way, with focus on the economic benefits, especially employment of biomass fired CHP boilers. Risks are mainly addressed in articles with an international focus, and in part of the comments of readers under the articles.

Figure 3-5: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 27 articles assessed in the Croatian media from January 2018 to April 2022

⁵⁷ <https://www.vecernji.hr/vijesti/fond-daje-do-35-000-kuna-za-nabavu-kotlova-na-biomasu-1285656>

⁵⁸ <https://www.jutarnji.hr/domidizajn/savjeti/stvari-u-koje-se-isplati-uloz-iti-investicije-zbog-kojih-c-e-vam-rez-ije-bit-smijes-no-male-15145215>

Table 3-3: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Croatian news articles on bioenergy.

Positive statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Bioenergy encourages growth and employment in the economy	6	16.7%
2. The use of biomass in Croatia unlocks bioeconomy development and enables rural development	2	5.6%
3. Bioenergy can contribute to reducing carbon emissions	2	5.6%
4. Bioenergy improves energy diversification	2	5.6%
5. Bioenergy is the most flexible renewable energy source	2	5.6%
Negative statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Bioenergy produces more greenhouse gas emissions than any other form of fossil energy	1	2.78%
2. Burning biomass in the EU emits a lot of carbon dioxide each year and could jeopardize the EU's 2050 climate neutrality goals	1	2.78%
3. It remains controversial whether wood-based biomass is an effective green fuel	1	2.78%
4. When using wood biomass, we must take into account the impact on biodiversity	1	2.78%
5. The national energy and climate plans of countries do not include the potential effects of the use of biomass on GHG emissions, biodiversity, and air and water pollution	1	2.78%

3.1.4 Romania

Policy analysis

In Romania, the growth of the renewable energy sector began once EU accession negotiations started and after the ratification of important strategic documents in Romanian law, which promoted the renewable energy sector and aimed at increasing the use of renewable energy. The next step in the process of promoting the energy production from renewable sources was the introduction of a support scheme based on a mandatory quota system and on trading green certificates through Government Decision (GD) no. 1892/2004 and subsequent amending government decisions. This support mechanism was then introduced by law 220/2008, and was authorized by the European Commission in June 2011⁵⁹ after several amendments and completions⁶⁰. The mandatory quotas system enforces a mandatory quota of RES-E to be bought by suppliers and sold to the consumers. The exact quantity of renewable electricity that is acquired is proved by purchased green certificates which can be traded on the national energy markets. More

⁵⁹ <http://energie.gov.ro/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/C2011-4938-final.pdf>

⁶⁰ <http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliiDocument/98742>

specifically, for each MWh of RES-E delivered to the grid, the producers receive a green certificate from the transport and system operator (Transelectrica) which can be subsequently traded on dedicated energy markets. The suppliers are obliged to fulfil the mandatory quotas by proving them with the number of green certificates purchased per year, calculated as the product of the mandatory yearly quota and the electricity provided that year. When energy suppliers do not comply with their quotas, they are penalized and the amount of money obtained from the fines is allocated to the Environmental Fund. This support mechanism applies to energy produced from wind, solar, geothermal, hydropower and biomass sources with an installed power equal or less than 10 MW. Before the support scheme was approved by the European Commission, the mechanism granted a single green certificate for each MWh produced and delivered to the grid. After approval, the allocation of green certificates was redefined. As of 2005, three green certificates were awarded for each MWh produced and delivered by biomass or bioliquids using cogeneration.

Yet, the predictability of the legal framework supporting the renewable energy sector was heavily impacted due to a few amendments adopted in 2012. The legal changes started with outlawing energy acquisition contracts outside of the regulated market, also known as Power Purchase Agreements (PPAs). The renewable energy sector suffered the most as they were using this type of contract to obtain the necessary funding to start renewable energy production projects. Other changes were the temporary postponement of green certificates trading, reducing the mandatory green certificate purchasing quota from 2014, decreasing the trading price and changing the tax provisions. Ultimately, the support scheme officially ended in 2016 as the target of 24% renewables share in the final energy consumption was met, and since then no further accreditation for new installed capacities was granted. As such, those who did not obtain an accreditation before December 2016, or newly installed renewable energy capacities after that date were no longer able to benefit from green certificates.

One of the positive changes was the extension of the validity period of trading green certificates until 31st of March 2032. The extension was necessary to halt financial losses incurred by the producers as a considerable number of certificates were expiring as they had not been traded. Still, financial losses were significant among renewable energy producers. In 2014-2015 alone, the wind sector registered losses of roughly €900 million⁶¹.

For the period 2014 until 2020, the development of the renewable energy sector was funded by the Operational Programme Large Infrastructure (LIOP) Priority axis 6; Objective 6.1: Increasing the production of energy from less exploited renewable energy sources (biomass, biogas, geothermal)⁶².

As every EU Member State is required to submit an Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan (INECP) for the period 2021-2030, Romania submitted its plan relating to the five dimensions of the Energy Union. The National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) foresees a total share of renewables in the gross final consumption of 30.7%. In order to achieve this objective, the NECP defines policies and measures to increase the share of RES-E, especially in the electricity and transport sectors. Most importantly, the plan defines support mechanisms to further develop the

⁶¹ <https://energy-center.ro/actualitate-news/cat-de-repede-au-trecut-investitorii-in-regenerabile-de-la-extaz-la-agonie-pierderi-de-4-miliarde-de-lei-in-industria-eoliana-in-anii-2014-si-2015/>

⁶² <http://mfe.gov.ro/programe/autoritati-de-management/am-poim/>

renewable energy sector, which includes the introduction of Contracts for Difference (CfD) and the re-legitimization of the PPAs. The national Plan does not mention renewable energy from biomass in particular. Yet, it gives priority to renewable energy from wind and solar⁶³.

Media analysis

The assessment of selected Romanian Newspapers (Libertatea, Evenimentul Zilei, Adevarul ("the Truth") and the English Romanian Journal) resulted in 16 articles in which the search term "biomass" was used in the context of bioenergy. Articles cover 2018 – 2022, with the main focus on the period from Jan 2021 to April 2022. The main findings are discussed below.

Many articles are dedicated to illegal logging, how to recognize it, and criticize the limited results of the state organisation that should fight illegal logging. These articles mainly use the term "biomass" to discuss the decrease in volume of forests, but do not directly relate to bioenergy, and thus included in the SPEED analysis. However, one article⁶⁴ "*A recent history of biomass. Episode 1*" stressed that the demand for firewood in the country is much higher than what can be legally provided and did make an explicit link with illegal logging. In addition, this article covers several other environmental risk factors as well, such as incorrect carbon accounting, doubt to start using for larger installations while the demand of firewood is already very high, removal of deadwood, the possible use of roundwood for energy. This article of August 2018 did not result in a further discussion on risks of bioenergy in the Romanian media.

The use of firewood in low efficient stoves by a large number of, mainly rural, households is seen as a problem, for which solutions must be found. In one article⁶⁵ the Minister of Environment advises to burn wood, like the Austrians do. "*In Austria, they still rely on wood, but on other technologies, shredding, pelletizing, automation, they greatly reduce emissions*". In the same article WWF Romania warns that the widespread use of wood for heating raises a sustainability issue and could even jeopardize the EU's environmental targets. According to this article the government is also criticized by NGOs for not having a large-scale policy for energy efficiency in housing.

Romania's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (EU's Corona funds) brings €14.2 billion in grants and €14.9 billion in loans to Romania under the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF). According to two articles^{66,67} one of the conditions set by the European commission is that Romania should give up inefficient firewood heating at homes by 2023, which would have a large impact on rural communities. This appeared to be fake news^{68,69}. The same Plan does include sustainability and traceability criteria for biomass used for energy, in order to prevent the negative

⁶³ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/default/files/documents/ro_final_necp_main_en.pdf

⁶⁴ https://adevarul.ro/international/europa/o-istorie-recenta-biomasei-episodul-1-1_5b60db92df52022f75dbf927/index.html

⁶⁵ <https://www.libertatea.ro/stiri/romania-mai-are-29-paduri-din-teritoriu-austria-are-48-dar-ministrul-mediului-ne-sfatuieste-sa-ardem-mai-mult-lemn-ca-austriecii-cat-ard-de-fapt-3950040>

⁶⁶ <https://evz.ro/se-interzice-definitiv-in-romania-pesto-80-din-populatie-va-fi-afectata-cu-ce-vor-fi-inlocuite-sobe-pe-lemn.html>

⁶⁷

⁶⁸ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/E-9-2021-005439-ASW_EN.html

⁶⁹ <https://www.euractiv.com/section/biomass/news/romania-wont-prohibit-wood-for-household-heating-energy-minister-says/>

impact of the use of bioenergy on biodiversity and forest ecosystems and to diversify the energy mix in the heating sector.

The use of non-woody biomass is generally perceived in a positive way. "The state should support larger thermal power plants that use sustainable biomass (manure, straw, sawdust) but not biomass currently used for firewood"⁷⁰. One article⁷¹ extensively discusses the success of the use of Scottish distilleries using biomass for energy and discusses the availability of agricultural residues in Romania, its potential and environmental benefits. Increasing the production of energy from less exploited renewable energy sources (biomass, biogas, geothermal) is seen as a good way forward. One article on a planned incineration plant of animal waste stresses it would be better to use it as resource for bioenergy, biogas and protein⁷².

Finally, the invasion of Ukraine has resulted in articles⁷³ summing up alternatives for (Russian) natural gas, which includes wind, solar, biomass and hydropower. One article⁷⁴ sums up the investment plans of the state-owned company Hidroelectrica, including bioelectricity production in a neutral way.

Analysis of the 16 articles on biomass resulted in 37 statements, of which 16 addressed risks, 10 covered benefits and 11 were neutral statements (See Figure 3-6). 15 statements were within the political SPEED frame, using the topic of biomass in relation to legislation, especially Romania's National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR). The environmental SPEED frame covered 11 statements, with 6 statement covering risks, of which 5 coming from the critical article "*A recent history of biomass. Episode 1*". The environmental benefits mentioned include GHG reduction and lower emissions compared to firewood combustion (Table 3-4). In the economic frame the benefits dominate, presenting bioenergy as an opportunity with potential for further development. The cultural aspect covers the possible change in the way of cooking/living if firewood would not be allowed anymore. The statement in the health and safety frame was related to the possible emissions of a poultry incineration plant. Remarkably, no statements on the health and safety risks of using firewood stoves at home were found.

⁷⁰ https://adevarul.ro/international/europa/o-istorie-recenta-biomasei-episodul-1-1_5b60db92df52022f75dbf927/index.html

⁷¹ <https://evz.ro/berea-solutia-minune-pentru-productia-de-energie-cum-ar-putea-rezolva-romania-criza-facturilor.html>

⁷² <https://evz.ro/pericol-de-poluare.html>

⁷³ <https://evz.ro/cum-poate-scapa-europa-de-dependenta-de-gazul-rusesc-solutiile-specialistilor.html>

⁷⁴ https://adevarul.ro/economie/investitii/parcuri-eoliene-largul-marii-productia-hidrogen-printre-investitiile-hidroelectrica-urmatorii-ani-1_5ec13aa65163ec4271dfc09d/index.html

Figure 3-6: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 16 articles assessed in the Romanian media from January 2018 to April 2022

Table 3-4: Number and share of positive and negative statements mentioned in Romanian news articles on bioenergy.

Positive statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Biomass produces renewable energy which emits less carbon and other pollutants compared to traditional fuels	4	10.8%
2. The use of biomass in Croatia unlocks bioeconomy development and Increasing energy generation through the use of biomass resulting from the production of wine or beer is an opportunity	3	8.1%
Negative statements	Nr. of statements	% of total
1. Through the PNRR, Romania has committed to the EU authorities to give up wood heating by 2023 and is now looking for solutions	2	5.4%

The overall picture shows concerns about the large use of firewood for low efficient for home heating and cooking, which is not linked strongly with deforestation/illegal logging. Use of non-woody biomass is seen as most positive.

3.1.5 Greece

Policy analysis

The first RES dedicated policy in Greece was Law 2244/1994. The provision laid down in this law coupled with the Licensing Code of December 2000, established the notion of 'Production Licence' as a fundamental prerequisite for all legal entities using RES in the electricity production. From 2000 and onwards, the production

license became the mandatory entry point to the administrative procedure for anyone aiming to become an electricity producer, except for very small RES installations (i.e., ranging from 20 to 500 kW of capacity). However, going through the entire process includes obtaining a production licence, installation licence and operation licence. Obtaining the installation and operation permits is conceived as complex decentralized administrative procedure.⁷⁵

As part of Greece's efforts to comply with European Union legislation, Law 3468/2006 promoted the electricity generation from renewable energy sources along with high-efficiency cogeneration of electricity and heat. This law aimed at establishing a clearer and transparent process in issuing licences and further promoting renewable energy investments. The statute included the environmental impact assessment (EIA) as integral part of the procedure of issuing the production licence, making it even more complex. The most important aspects of this Law were the establishment of a national target to achieve a 20.1% share of renewables of their total domestic power consumption by 2010, new feed-in tariffs were defined, and it improved the terms for sale of renewables-based electricity (i.e., 10-year validity of PPAs could be extended for an equal period) in order to facilitate bank financing.

According to Law 3851/2010, the Greek National Renewable Energy Action Plan raised its commitments to produce 20% of the final energy consumption and 40% electricity generation from renewable sources by 2020. A crucial part of the 2010 strategy was to accelerate the licensing process whereby the authorities were required to meet mandatory deadlines. The most important changes concerned the production license, the first stage in the approval process. The license was issued by the regulatory authority which had a two-month deadline. In addition, a preliminary EIA was no longer required. Instead, only one assessment would be required to apply for the installation license. The authorities were only given four months to provide their decision based on the EIA. The whole licensing process can not last longer than 30 months.⁷⁶

During the period 2006-2015, Greece promoted the production of electricity from RES through a FiT programme. Law 3468/2006, amended by Law 3851/2010 and significantly revised by Law 4254/2014 to introduce technology and project specific criteria, initialised the programme in 2006. Generally, the tariffs saw an upward trend, except for solar PV as the investment costs were significantly reduced. Greece closed the FiT programme on the 31st of December 2015.

In August 2016, the Greek Parliament passed the new national support scheme for electricity from renewables and highly efficient cogeneration of heat and power by virtue of Law 4414/2016. According to the new policy, all types of new renewable energy plants connected to the grid after the 1st of January 2016 need to participate in the energy market. Their compensation is based on a variable Feed-in Premium (FiP). The latter is the difference between a price depending on market variables and a set price decided via a competitive tender. There are, however, some exemptions to these new policies. Firstly, projects using RES having capacities smaller than 500 kW can still apply for a FiT. Agreements based either on a FiT or following a FiP are valid for 20 years, except solar thermal plants which are

⁷⁵ The evolution of renewable energy sources in the electricity of Greece, Dimitris Manolopoulos, et al; International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, 2016.

⁷⁶ <https://www.iea.org/policies/5052-renewable-energy-law-3851?country=Greece&page=1&q=Gree>

compensated for 25 years. Finally, projects having signed PPAs with Greek institutions before the 31st of December 2015 are not required to participate in the energy market and can still apply under the previous policy scheme (FIT).⁷⁷

Until 2013, all RES technologies except for solar PVs could apply for investment subsidies. More specifically, Law 4146/2013 limited subsidies only to investments plans in (pumped) hydro, hybrid, biomass, and biogas installations that were submitted after the 1st of January 2014. Yet, all RES technologies were eligible for tax incentives. According to the new Development Law (4399/2016), investment subsidies will be granted to, amongst others, high-efficiency co-generation plants using RES.⁷⁸

In the last decade, Greece has experienced a deep recession as a result of the financial crisis and subsequent politics of austerity. The crisis had a significant impact on the development of renewable energies. Consequently, Greece has not met its 2020 target of 40% renewables in the electricity mix. In order to pick up the pace again, the current government led by the conservative Nea Dimokratia radically changed the draft Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) which lays out Greece's climate and energy target for 2030. All of the main targets were revised upwards in the final NECP, in some cases quite substantially. Furthermore, the new Greek government decided to speed up the exit from coal-fired power generation by 2028⁷⁹. Last decisions from recent government suggest that wind energy and solar PV are the priority sources for renewable energy in Greece. Case in point, the new environmental law 4685/2020 aims to speed up the environmental permitting process through measures such as allowing the development of PV plants with a generation capacity of up to 1 MW without an environmental license⁸⁰. Furthermore, the Greek recovery plan following the Covid pandemic, includes investments (i.e., €1 billion) in PV arrays in particular⁸¹.

Media analysis

The assessment of selected Greek newspapers (Kathimerini, To Vima, Ta Nea⁸²) resulted in 42 articles in which the search term "biomass" was used in the context of bioenergy. Articles cover 2018 – 2022. The main findings are discussed below.

Eight articles cover the heating allowance that Greek households can obtain under certain conditions to compensate for high fossil oil prices. Consumers using firewood and biomass (pellets), only get the heating allowance if the property is located in a settlement with a population equal to or less than 2,500 inhabitants.

Six articles describe the plans and activities of PPC Renewables (PPCR), a wholly owned subsidiary of the Public Power Corporation SA (PPC), Greece's largest power generation company⁸³. PPCR claims to be the only company in Greece active on all

⁷⁷ <https://www.renewableenergyworld.com/baseload/greece-approves-new-renewable-energy-law/#gref>

⁷⁸ Energy policies of IEA countries, Greece 2017 Review. International Energy Agency

⁷⁹ <https://energytransition.org/2020/04/a-wind-of-change-for-greeces-energy-transition/>

⁸⁰ <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2020/07/01/greek-ev-policy-follows-on-the-heels-of-environmental-package/>

⁸¹ <https://www.pv-magazine.com/2021/04/01/greeces-recovery-plan-to-invest-e10bn-in-clean-energy/>

⁸² Online articles of To Vima and Ta Nea showed high overlap and may come from the same source. In case of identical articles, the article was analysed only once.

⁸³ <https://www.ppcr.gr/en/company/profile-background-strategy>

forms of renewable energy sources, namely wind, solar, hydroelectric, geothermal, and biomass. Three articles cover an Expression of Interest for companies willing to cooperate with PPCR to construct and operate a biomass plant in Amyteo, Florina. The technical, economic, environmental and health and safety benefits are briefly described. The other articles mainly describe the role of PPCR in the energy transition in the coming years, in which bioenergy is touched upon briefly in a rather neutral way as one of the renewable energy options.

Eight articles covered bioenergy in the context of the planned ban on lignite combustion by 2018, especially in relation to the planned (coal fired) "Ptolemaida 5" plant. In four articles biomass is described in a neutral way as one of the options (along with natural gas, garbage, hydrogen) to replace coal. One article⁸⁴ stresses the health benefit of biomass compared to coal and one article states that renewables including biomass will be cheaper than fossil fuels⁸⁵.

The number of articles dedicated solely to bioenergy was limited to 2 out of 42 articles. Next to the already mentioned article⁸⁶ on the request for Expressions of Interest for the planned biomass plant in Amyteo, one article⁸⁷ addresses the possibility of bioenergy production from straw that remains unclaimed after the end of the growing season, in the frame of the publication of a CRES study. Both articles stress especially the economic and technical benefits of bioenergy.

The remaining articles containing "biomass" covered various topics, like investments of Spain in renewables from the European Recovery Fund, the plans of the European Commission to reduce the EU's dependence from energy imports from Russia, a study on the costs of various domestic heating systems in the frame of the high energy prices in autumn 2021, and the fact that the UK didn't use coal for one week in May 2019 for power production, which is the first time since the industrial revolution. In all these articles biomass was mentioned in a rather neutral way together with other renewable energy options.

In general, the topic of bioenergy is addressed in a rather neutral to positive way, which is confirmed by the SPEED analysis. Analysis of the 42 articles on biomass resulted in 44 statements, of which only 2 addressed risks, 15 covered benefits and 27 were neutral statements. Figure 3-7 shows that 15 statements were within the political SPEED frame, using the topic of biomass in a neutral way related to legislation and targets, especially the heating allowance for households. Economic and technical statements were all set in a neutral or benefit frame, mainly in the presentation of factual information. Compared to the other investigated countries, the environmental SPEED frame is not much used in the media. Two articles state that bioenergy is "environmentally friendly". Also, the number of negative statements is limited to only two, one health and safety risk on smog, and one environmental risk on climate neutrality of bioenergy.

⁸⁴ <https://www.tovima.gr/2018/02/24/finance/filiki-methodos-paragwgis-energeias-apo-fysika-kaysima/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.tovima.gr/2019/07/29/society/n-xaralampidis-sto-one-channel-den-ekdikeitai-i-fysi-einai-ola-anthropina-erga/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.tovima.gr/2018/02/24/finance/filiki-methodos-paragwgis-energeias-apo-fysika-kaysima/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.tovima.gr/2018/05/05/finance/ilektriki-energeia-apo-axyro-sto-thessaliko-kampo/>

Figure 3-7: Amount of SPEED Risk and Benefits Frames mentioned in all 42 articles assessed in the Greek media from January 2018 to April 2022

Comparison and reporting of the specific statements was impractical due to the low number of positive and negative frames. The overall picture shows a rather low coverage of bioenergy in the Greek media. If bioenergy is addressed, it is mainly in a neutral or slightly positive way.

3.2 Literature analysis of Community acceptance

The concept of community acceptance

Community acceptance is decisive for the success and sustainability of RES, as local opposition can lead to increasing costs and delays⁸⁸, or even the cancellation of projects. Therefore, it is important to understand and anticipate the factors that underlie major social barriers, which may affect the acceptance and implementation of renewable energy technologies (González et al 2016). Community acceptance is a multidimensional concept that is difficult to grasp using a single definition. However, it can be summarised as the approval of an act and the willingness to work towards its perpetuation for the future (Gonzalez et al 2016).

Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) have identified that community acceptance of a renewable energy project can be influenced by factors related to three categories, namely: distributional justice (sharing burdens and benefits fairly), procedural justice (fair treatment in fair processes, e.g., in permit procedures) and trust (of community members in involved authorities, experts and companies).

Regarding **distributional justice**, in the realisation of a new renewable energy facility, the municipality may be among the winners as the plant contributes to regional renewable energy targets. If any community members lose, it will be people living near the plant (Ganzevles et al. 2015). Opposition from local actors to projects has been depicted in the literature as the “NIMBY” (not in my back yard) phenomenon.

Procedural justice is about fair treatment in fair processes. Standard legal frameworks enable members of communities to react to requests for permits which are needed for setting up the renewable energy facility. There is, however, often no direct (financial) participation of people living nearby.

The **trust** of community members in the renewable energy facility does not depend on justice aspects only. Trust can be defined as the expectation that arises within a community of regular, honest, and cooperative behaviour, based on commonly shared norms (Paletto et al 2019)⁸⁹. Another important aspect is the trust in expertise (Ganzevles et al. 2015). For example, experts saying that pyrolysis oil storage is safe is no guarantee that people living nearby will perceive it as being safe. Misinformation can easily be spread by lay people via blogs and social media, where it can contribute to unfounded concerns.

Community acceptance of bioenergy versus other technologies

The availability of literature on community preferences of renewable energy technologies including CHP are limited. A useful source is, however, Jung et al. (2016)⁹⁰, which provides a comparison of the acceptability of several renewable energy options, based on an online survey answered by 246 respondents in

⁸⁸ Example: <https://www.parool.nl/amsterdam/biomassacentrale-diemen-krijgt-groen-licht-van-rechter~b458a9f4f/>

⁸⁹ Paletto, A, S. Bernardi, E. Pieratti, F. Teston, M. Romagnoli (2019) Assessment of environmental impact of biomass power plants to increase the social acceptance of renewable energy technologies, *Heliyon* 5 (2019) e02070

⁹⁰ Jung, N., M. Moula, T. Fang, M. Hamdy, R. Lahdelma (2016) Social acceptance of renewable energy technologies for buildings in the Helsinki Metropolitan Area of Finland. *Renewable Energy* 99 (2016) 813-824

Helsinki. Figure 3-8 shows how the respondents ranked the various options. Solar PV, ground source heat pumps and solar water heaters are the most accepted technologies. Wood chips CHP (CHPR) and Waste based CHP (CHPW) remained the least opted for among the respondents. The reasoning behind this result could be based on the fact that end users, in general, are not very involved in Finland; these alternatives are large scale plants owned by big companies. Micro-scale wood chips CHP and community waste-based CHP production units are not common in Finland because the investments are relatively high, and the return is low. CHP was supported by respondents employed at energy companies. A reason for low acceptance of Waste based CHP (CHPW) could be due to an infamous waste incineration plant near the city centre which polluted its surroundings. This plant was shut down in 1983 due to citizen movement (Jung et al 2016).

Abbreviation	RET alternative provided for ranking
SOLAR	Solar electricity by photovoltaic cells
GSHP	Ground source heat pump
SHEAT	Solar heat for space heating and domestic hot water
SHEATP	Combination of a solar thermal system for space heating, domestic hot water, and electric power
CHPR	Combined heat and power production based on renewable biomass such as wood chips, etc.
WINDS	Small scale wind turbine
CHPW	Combined heat and power production based on community waste
WINDR	Roof mounted small scale wind turbine

Figure 3-8: Rank acceptability indices for RET alternatives, showing the variety of possible preferences that place alternatives on different ranks. Alternatives are sorted according to their first rank acceptability index. Source: Jung et al. (2016)

The role of location

Proka et al (2014)⁹¹ investigated the link between the size of Dutch biomass CHP plants and techno-economic, environmental performance as well as social acceptance. Their findings on location and participation are worth mentioning.

The findings of this study suggest that location is a critical factor behind the attitude of people towards biomass plants, which is of high importance for both small and large-scale plants. People's attitude is indirectly affected by scale as small-scale plants are usually located closer to residential areas. When the plant is not at the immediate proximity of the local community, then, as no direct effect takes place, people seem to be indifferent of scale.

The role of participation

There is ample evidence that local involvement, especially local co-ownership, decreases negative perceptions and dramatically increases public acceptance (Musall and Kuik 2011)⁹². Interestingly, models for co-production and co-ownership as currently widely applied with onshore wind have as yet not been considered for CHP biomass plants in the Netherlands (Proka et al 2014). In 2021, this is still the case although the topic of participation as such gains more and more attention in the setup and implementation of the Regional Energy Strategies that are currently under development in the Netherlands. Participation could play a role if SmartCHP is implemented in residential buildings. In tertiary sectors, agriculture or industry it may be more straightforward if only the owner of the company or building participates in a SmartCHP project. In many cases these owners are part of the local community, contrary to wind and solar parks which are often financed by foreign investors.

Community acceptance of physical impacts of SmartCHP

Next to generic factors such as distributional and procedural justice, trust, the socio-political acceptance of bioenergy, the role of location and participation, it can be assumed that community acceptance of SmartCHP depends on its physical characteristics of the SmartCHP system and its impacts to the local environment.

In contrast to solar and wind energy, bioenergy is less visible for the community as space requirements are limited. Disturbances of the landscape will be limited to a chimney and possibly a visible storage tank. Disadvantages of bioenergy compared to many other renewable energy solutions are emissions of especially dust, NO_x, and possibly the smell of smoke. It is important to stress that the end-of-pipe emissions of the SmartCHP system will be very low and will cause no smell. The SmartCHP system should not be associated to howe owned wood stoves. Increased transport movements can cause disturbances and are often arranged in permits. In case of a 2 MW input SmartCHP systems operating 7000 hours/year would require about 158 trucks with 20 tonnes of FPBO/year. Whether this is acceptable also depends on the local situation. The odour of pyrolysis oil is rather strong. Therefore, during filling of the storage tanks the release of vapours should

⁹¹ Proka, A., M. Hisschemöller and E. Papyrakis (2014) The scale of transition: an integrated study of the performance of CHP biomass plants in the Netherlands, *Journal of Integrative Environmental Sciences*, 11:3-4, 225-241, DOI: 10.1080/1943815X.2014.966113

⁹² Musall FD, Kuik O. 2011. Local acceptance of renewable energy – a case study from southeast Germany. *Energy Policy*. 39:3252–3260.

be limited, for instance by a vapour return system. It can be anticipated that all the above impacts are more acceptable in an industrial area than in a residential area.

Table 3-5: List of concerns of communities on implementation of bioenergy projects and estimated relevance for community acceptance SmartCHP.

Community's concerns	Relevant in # of cases (out of 8)	Relevant for SmartCHP?
Related to the issue of siting		
• Location of the power plant	2	Y
• Growing of biomass crops near to residences	2	N
• Close proximity to local residents	2	Y
Related to the issue of emissions and health hazards		
• Emission of GHG and water vapour	3	Y
• Unpleasant odour	5	Y
• Emission of light at night	3	Maybe
• Nuisance / pollution from traffic	3	Y
• Vibrations and noise from power plant	8	Y
• Fear for public health hazards	2	Y
• Local air pollution	4	Y
Related to the issue of transport		
• Traffic is an issue (in general)	4	Y
• Increase in traffic movement & heavy vehicles	4	Y
• Accidents and noise due to traffic	2	Y
Related to the issue of environmental/ecological effects		
• Fear of negative impacts on biodiversity	4	Y
• Negative effect on local weather system	2	Y
• Local environment is threatened	2	Y
Related to the issue of landscape and agriculture		
• Landscape and agricultural change	2	N
• Undermining openness [of landscape]	2	N
• Visual effects of relative height of buildings, chimney, plants and other associated structures	7	Y
Related to the issue of economic effects		
• Low/no benefits to local community compared to associated social and environmental costs	3	Y
• Negative effects to tourism, business and livestock	3	Y
• Compensation on dispute	2	Y
• Negative impacts on property prices	5	Y
• No significant employment opportunity to local people	2	Y
Other concerns		
• Industrial precedent & large-scale infrastructure associated with production	2	Y
• Low public confidence about the technological reliability	2	Y

Source: Eswaral et al. (2014). The last column is added by and based on the authors' estimate.

To validate the above - ad hoc - analysis of acceptance factors of physical community acceptance factors, it is helpful to assess which factors were regarded

relevant in other bioenergy installations. Eswarlal et al. (2014)⁹³ performed a literature search related to community acceptance of 8 bioenergy projects located in the USA and Europe, documented in 15 published works dating from 2002 – 2012. Table 3-5 shows which aspects were mentioned and in how many of the 8 projects they occurred. Issues that appeared only once have been removed, avoiding a long list of very specific concerns. In the right column, the possible relevance of these projects for SmartCHP has been indicated. Only issues that are very unlikely to be relevant, as they may only occur with large scale bioenergy plants, have been indicated not relevant.

3.3 Literature analysis of Market acceptance

As announced in sections 1.3 and 2.3 on approach and methodology, the market acceptance assessment will be based on interviews, supported by literature on motivations, barriers and other influential factors of microgeneration.

Motivations and barriers of market acceptance of microgeneration systems

A fair amount of scientific work is performed on the consumer perception and adoption of microgeneration technologies. Although decision making on the investment in SmartCHP equipment will take place at organization level instead of at homeowner level, the overview will serve as a good basis for the foreseen exploratory interviews.

Most studies use survey data based on hypothetical questions (e.g., asking about potential future behaviour), whereas a smaller number of studies use data based on stated preferences in past decisions. Motivations and barriers were often classified in gain (e.g., economic advantages, ease of use); normative motivations (e.g., environmental commitment, neighbours' disapproval), hedonic aspects (e.g., fun, short term satisfaction, image); and other influencing factors (e.g., availability of space, impact on residence, life phase of the respondent, voluntariness of decision making). Within the literature the classification could not always be made very strictly, for instance, environmental commitment has gain (GHG reduction), normative (e.g., others care about the planet and so do I) and hedonic elements (e.g., showing off). Below in Table 3-6, Table 3-7 and Table 3-8 the main motivations and barriers to implementation of microgeneration technologies as well as other influencing factors are summarised, as collected by Vis (2018) from various sources (i.e., Balcombe et al (2013), Caird and Roy (2010), Dóci & Vasileiadou (2015), Garcia et al. (2015), Hecker et al. (2017), Jolivet et al (2009), Forest et al. (2013), Gold (2011)). In the right column the expected relevance for potential buyers of SmartCHP systems (e.g., organisations in tertiary, industrial, agricultural and large residential sectors) are indicated, to be further explored in the interviews.

⁹³ Eswarlal, V, G. Vasudevan, P. Dey, P. Vasudevan (2014) Role of community acceptance in sustainable bioenergy projects in India, *Energy Policy*, Volume 73, october 2014 Pages 333 – 343, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0301421514002353?via%3Dihub> (for free access:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262806403_Role_of_community_acceptance_in_sustainable_bioenergy_projects_in_India

Table 3-6: Barriers to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.

Barrier	Relevant for SmartCHP buyers?
High capital cost of the installation is an important barrier, as well as long payback periods. This could be partly levied with subsidies.	Yes
Difficulties to refit the house to make microgeneration possible is an important barrier, e.g., a fuel storage space, boiler space and chimney are needed.	Yes
Uncertainty about performance and reliability is an important aspect that needs to be addressed properly, for instance by proper after sales service.	Yes
Hassle of installation (duration and possible mess), and disruption of the garden.	Yes, especially in public and residential buildings
Ease of use is important. The system should operate with the lowest need for manual operation possible.	Yes, especially in public and residential buildings
Transaction costs, e.g., the need to put much effort in finding information, the right system and installer, the possible need of a planning permit form a barrier.	Yes

Source: Vis (2018) collected from various sources, see main text.

Table 3-7: Motivations to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.

Motivation	Relevant for SmartCHP buyers?
Saving money on the heating costs on the long run, by tax exemptions, subsidies, and/or lower fuel bills is of course an important driver.	Yes
Environmental motivations are a main driver to invest in microgeneration as well. This does not only cover GHG reduction, but also helping the next generation, and showing environmental commitment to others.	Maybe
Security of supply: the feeling of being independent of large companies, having access to your own energy, is an important driver as well. There may be a certain risk that in case of pyrolysis oil, where dependence on one or few pyrolysis oil suppliers will take place, this motivation is not properly addressed.	Maybe
Personal interest in sustainability and technology, using an innovative/high-tech system, the will to support the development of renewable energy technologies can be motivations for part of the potential buyers. Educative and patriotic motivations were also mentioned.	Maybe
Social aspects were important especially when initiatives were performed in a group: getting to know more people within the	Maybe in locations owned or used by

community, feeling part of a group, fun to take the challenge together, as well as lower transaction costs.	groups (residential buildings)
---	--------------------------------

Source: Vis (2018) collected from various sources, see main text

Table 3-8: Other influencing factors to implementation of microgeneration technologies and their expected relevance for SmartCHP systems.

Motivation	Relevant for SmartCHP buyers?
Awareness of the existence of the product is the starting point of any possible adoption decision.	Yes
Homeowners who chose alternative heating systems consult a significantly higher number of information channels and more actively searched for information than homeowners who adopted fossil systems. Consequently, homeowners with alternative heating systems are more influenced by specialized information, the internet, and their social networks, whereas homeowners who chose fossil systems are more influenced by installers.	Maybe
In case of new unknown systems, homeowners need to have a chance to see and touch heating systems, for instance at trade fairs.	Yes
The number of homeowners in a new building situation have the highest adoption rate of alternative heating systems compared to the other groups.	Maybe
Between 45-65 years, a visible increase in microgeneration installations up to the retirement age was found, which could possibly be explained by available income.	Maybe age of decision maker has some impact
Adoption of microgeneration is more prevalent in larger houses, as these have a higher energy use, more space to incorporate a microgeneration system, and the owner might have a higher household income.	Yes, companies that have high turnover and profit have more possibilities to buy the system
Next to income, social class could play a role. It is suggested that the academic elite is more interested in solar panels, while farmers and skilled manual workers are more interested in a biomass fuelled system.	Maybe. In case of smart CHP, industrial clients may be more interested than tertiary and residential sector.

Source: Vis (2018) collected from various sources, see main text

Market acceptance of pyrolysis oil for residential heating

Next to this generic overview of motivations and barriers, within the Residue2Heat project, 15 in depth interviews were held with respondents in the Netherlands, Belgium and Germany, who were owners of gas, oil or pellet boilers for residential heating (Vis 2018). In order to get the original ideas and deeper motivations of the respondents, instead of showing a list of all possible motivations and barriers, the respondents reacted on triads (a paper containing some characteristics of three different heating systems, e.g., a gas, oil and FPBO boiler). Subsequently the respondents' reaction is asked, followed by "why" questions. The range of answers to the why questions form ladders from which the relevant attributes can be obtained. In data analysis based on the interviews, Kelly' triad, laddering and relation schemes were used as data analysis techniques; 17 attributes elicited from

ladders were analysed: i.e. environmental benefit, convenience, regional aspects, price, central heating system versus stove, new ideas (new technology), alternatives, new system, social impact, certification, autonomy, hedonic value, distrust, efficiency, features of oil/pellets, information and safety. A relation scheme was drawn to give insights of a big picture and to analyse the relation between the above-mentioned attributes, respectively. Below the main results of the interviews are summarised, plus our estimation if this is relevant for market acceptance of SmartCHP:

- **Price:** consumers can understand they should pay more if they want a new convenient and sustainable heating system, benefitting from new technology. People have psychological anticipation of a higher price. No respondent said he or she wants a better system while a lower price is also a must. It is encouraging for the FPBO concept that consumers understand this. However, if the motivation of adopting a new sustainable system is not strong enough, a higher price becomes a barrier for many consumers who don't have very high income. This will be relevant for SmartCHP as well.
- **Environmental benefit:** experts among the respondents are doubting and questioning the environmental benefit of pyrolysis oil. However, in general lay consumers believe pyrolysis oil is a very good choice to benefit environment and nature. In case of questions related to sustainability, it is good to emphasise that a residual wood is used and not stemwood, as consumers don't like whole trees being cut down for energy. This perception is expected to be related to the socio-political acceptance in the SmartCHP focus country.
- **Convenience** is perceived to be one of the most important concerns of consumers. The pyrolysis boiler should be easy to operate, cost less effort and time than pellet heaters, and work automatically. Generally speaking, people want to be lazy at home and spend their free time to something else than operating a heating system. In case of SmartCHP this will be highly relevant, especially if normally no skilled personal is available in the building.
- **Innovativeness** of a new product has two sides. New technology and new ideas inspire people; consumers believe innovativeness can benefit environment and nature. However, marketers should be careful when using innovativeness in marketing. It cannot be denied consumers are concerned about reliability of a product based on new ideas. Not all the people want to be pioneers. This aspect is expected to be relevant in case of SmartCHP as well. It may depend more on the character of the decision makers than on the type of business.
- **"Local product"** is mostly taken as a positive label related to environmental benefit, convenience, lower price, etc. This is true for the heating system, and maybe even more for the pyrolysis oil as a fuel. If the biomass is based locally, to prove this with evidence is important. Moreover, it is important to explain that the local country has sufficient biomass available. It would be highly interesting to explore if this aspect plays a role in SmartCHP as well.

- **Product properties:** it is important to prove that the product is safe and efficient. The (Belgian and German) fuel oil adopters interviewed had negative perception towards the oil product, regarding it dirty and out-of-fashion. It is important to put pyrolysis oil in the market as a modern and green fuel, very different from fuel oil. This perception could be relevant in case of SmartCHP as well. Therefore, it is recommended during the interviews to note down information on the current energy carriers that are used for heat and electricity.
- **Information:** most lay consumers have almost no idea about pyrolysis oil. To adopt a heating system is a big decision, for which much cognitive effort is needed. When consumers are not aware of the technology and product, they are not in the position to judge, and not make a further decision. Therefore, it is key to offer comprehensive information to consumers, and take care that they find additional information from different sources when they search the internet. This is expected to be highly relevant in SmartCHP as well.

Quantitative assessment of motivations and barriers of microgeneration systems

A recent quantitative assessment of factors affecting sustainable market acceptance of residential microgeneration technologies in Greece was performed by Karytsas et al (2019). Figure 3-9 shows the perceived importance of factors related to consumers' behavior, preferences and attitudes for residential microgeneration technologies, based on a survey held in Greece in 2012 and 2019.

It can be observed that "functional reliability", "system lifetime" and "secure installation, equipment and operation" are regarded as very important. These and other mentioned could be included in the interviews with potential end users as well.

Figure 3-9: perceived importance of factors related to consumers' behavior, preferences and attitudes for residential microgeneration technologies. Source: Karytsas et al. (2019)

The role of interfirm acceptance

In Ganzevles et al (2015)⁹⁴ three conceptual categories of market acceptance have been identified: intra-firm acceptance; acceptance by investors; and acceptance by consumers. It was observed that the intra-firm acceptance can be lower if new concepts (such as a biorefinery approach instead of a straightforward bioenergy approach) are introduced in which dependence on other business partners outside the traditional business chain is increased. In the paper the term inter-firm trust was introduced to cover this aspect. In case of SmartCHP, the end user will need to trust the supplier of pyrolysis oil and the installer of the equipment.

Overview of main acceptance factors

The selected literature in this section gives an overview of market acceptance which are expected to be relevant for the introduction of SmartCHP systems in the five focus countries.

Figure 3-10: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.

The degree of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance of bioenergy project in general as investigated in chapters 3 and 4 also impact the market acceptance as illustrated in Figure 3-10.

⁹⁴ Ganzevles, J, L. Asveld and P.Osseweijer (2015) Extending bioenergy towards smart biomass use Issues of social acceptance at Park Cuijk, The Netherlands, Sustainability and Society (2015) 5:22 DOI 10.1186/s13705-015-0053-9

3.4 Interviews with stakeholders

3.4.1 Results of the requests for interviews in the 5 focus countries

Overall, 85 organizations were contacted for interviews, but the response rate was very low and resulted in 11 interviews with different organizations in all 5 countries with Greece having the highest response rate (4 positive responses out of 20 requests sent) and the Netherlands having the lowest (1 positive response out of 15 sent). The response rates for all countries are presented in Table 3-9 here below.

Table 3-9: Interview request' response rate by country

Country	Number of contacted stakeholders	Response rate
Croatia	14	14%
Greece	20	20%
Sweden	20	15%
Romania	16	13%
The Netherlands	15	7%

The distribution per type of respondent by country is presented in Table 3-10 here below:

Table 3-10: Number and type of respondents by country

Country	Number of respondents	Type of respondents
Croatia	2	Socio-political
Greece	4	3 Socio-political; 1 End-user (promoter*)
Sweden	3	2 Socio-political; 1 End-user
Romania	2	1 Socio-political; 1 End-user (promoter*)
The Netherlands	1	1 End-user (promoter*)

*Company which would not directly make use of the technology but that could promote it to clients (both public and private)

3.4.2 Analysis

Considering the number of interviews conducted and the non-homogeneity of the type of respondents per country. The analysis of the interviews cannot be deemed as conclusive and can neither support drawing relevant and accurate conclusions on the level of acceptance of SmartCHP as a technology or bioenergy as a whole in a country nor constitute basis for a comparison among the five focus countries. Nevertheless, the responses received by countries were analysed and the highlights are presented by country in the following paragraphs.

Croatia

- **Perception:** Bioenergy is considered as an important contributor to achieve the country's decarbonization target and improvements are deemed necessary especially in terms of efficiency as most CHPs in the country are

oriented towards maximum electricity production and minimum heat production and none fits the RED II criteria. A new technology such as SmartCHP would be more accepted as there is no more trust in the technologies in place (The performance of the previous CHP on previous biomass was so low that there is no more support for it).

- **Risks and Barriers:** Besides the cost, the performance and the maintenance that could be challenging, a main barrier resides in the fact that about 85% of the forests are public making it the largest biomass supplier (emphasis on the importance of good forest management for the quality of the material to be used). Moreover, when loans are provided for large scale CHPs the contractual agreements necessitate that 70% of the supply will come from the public forest, very little room for other sources of biomass. On a different note, the European Commission revoked the Feed-in tariff stimulation model and introduced the system of premium incentives which exposes producers of electricity from renewable sources to market risks.
- **Motivation factors:** The motivation can be fostered by a stable regulatory framework and policy as well as a reliable market. As for sectors that could make most use of the technology, District heating and industries were mentioned.
- **Facilitating conditions:** Supporting schemes for buildings and the need for refurbishment and renovation in the country could make it a good market for SmartCHP.

Greece

- **Perception:** Although specific targets related to bioenergy in the country exist it remains low in the political agenda in comparison with other RES. 3000MW capacity planned of which only 105MW is installed meaning that the country would need to build 20 plants of 1MW per year which seems highly unlikely especially considering the overall issues with RES integration. Improvements are deemed needed but no specific ones are mentioned. The technology is perceived as polluting, costly and requiring a lot of space.
- **Risks and Barriers:** The lack of availability of biomass is flagged as the main barrier requiring the mobilization and organization of the agricultural sector. Cost and Maintenance were also identified as issues as well as the seasonality of cultures in Greece which can impact fuel composition. The policy framework is not deemed conducive and the level of awareness and communication around the technology is very low which hinders social acceptance.
- **Motivation factors:** Support schemes and incentive programs are deemed to be the most effective motivation, apart from tariffs additional gate fees for biomass collected should be considered so that farmers can be paid and it would be an incentive to provide and transport the waste from agricultural production. Sectors that could make most use of the technology are identified as hospitals, hotels, residential district heating.
- **Facilitating conditions:** Feed-in tariff.

Sweden

- **Perception:** Bioenergy is a major energy source in the country where the focus is more on the electrification rather than biofuels. It is a forest country, yet the resources do not seem to be optimally exploited resulting in waste.
- **Risks and Barriers:** The policy and regulatory framework are not deemed conducive or supportive of bioenergy projects. Emphasis on requirement to adhere to EU law hindering the progress and support of bioenergy in the country. Since it is not allowed to burn wood, some companies are importing waste from countries like Poland. The cost and insurance issues for installation in existing plants were raised, the cost of bio-CHP plants is deemed too high and very few units are up and running. The biofuels market is deemed insecure especially for those from forestry which is the strength of the country. Sectors that could potentially be of interest would be the industry and municipalities. It is worth mentioning that risks and barriers are perceived very differently by the two entities interviewed.
- **Motivation factors:** Support schemes and more stringent maluses imposition on CO₂ generation as those existing are deemed insufficient.
- **Facilitating conditions:** RED II and looking into RED III for the transport sector as well as tax exemption as support to biofuels. Climate step program.

Romania

- **Perception:** *Although bioenergy projects have great potential considering the availability of biomass (forest, agriculture, waste), it is not supported at all by the government and by the policy. Only a few projects exist where some livestock residues are used to produce biogas producing power and heat.*
- **Risks and Barriers:** The cost is considered as the primary issue followed by maintenance.
- **Motivation factors:** National policy is deemed as having the strongest influence and the main motivation factor. The sectors that would be of interest include District heating, hospitals, and hotels.
- **Facilitating conditions:** None to the knowledge of the interviewees.

The Netherlands

- **Perception:** Although everything seems to be in place in the country in terms of targets and policies the development of bioenergy projects is behind. There is a strong anti-biomass lobby in the country especially for the cutting of forests. It will only be developed on the market if the government supports it.
- **Risks and Barriers:** The main barriers appear to be the financing as there is no visibility concerning support schemes for such projects. The process for the project development is also generally deemed very slow and the

certification scheme is not achieved through the government it is validated by an external company.

- **Motivation factors:** With all coal power plants that will be closed by 2030 all companies are looking for what could be self-supporting for them so SmartCHP could be a solution combined with other technologies. There are market opportunities for hospitals, schools etc.
- **Facilitating conditions:** Existing incentives for the application of pyrolysis oil.

4. Public acceptance strategy

Based on the main findings of this study, this chapter presents a possible public acceptance strategy that can be followed during and after the market introduction of SmartCHP systems, focussing on socio-political, community and market acceptance, which are interlinked as illustrated in Figure 4-1.

Figure 4-1: The anticipated role of socio-political acceptance and community acceptance on market acceptance of SmartCHP systems. Source: own elaboration.

4.1 Socio-Political acceptance

Netherlands

From the perspective of socio-political acceptance of bioenergy, the Netherlands is the riskiest of the five focus countries to introduce SmartCHP technology. Negative perceptions prevail, which already impacted the availability of renewable energy subsidies for future bioenergy CHP installations⁹⁵.

Sweden

Sweden has a large and well-developed bioenergy sector, and although discussion on the risks and benefits of bioenergy is present in the media, this discussion has more the character of an exchange of pros and cons than is the case in the Netherlands. Overall, in Sweden, the share of risk statements is 55% and benefit statements 45%. Given the vast experience with the use of woody biomass in Sweden, the social acceptance risk is expected to be relatively low.

⁹⁵ The current SDE++ subsidy requires for example that heat has at least a temperature of 100 °C, new biomass CHP or heat only plants for hot water (district heating) will not be subsidised anymore.

Croatia

Media coverage in Croatia is rather low but positive. In Croatia, several CHP systems have been or will be installed, which was presented in news articles in a neutral to positive manner. The introduction of SmartCHP technology using miscanthus based pyrolysis is expected to be socially acceptable in Croatia.

Greece

In Greece, the number of bioenergy installations and thus its coverage in news articles is rather low, but positive. The ban on coal does make larger industries to move to other renewables including bioenergy. The introduction of olive residue-based pyrolysis oil for SmartCHP systems is expected to be possible without socio-political acceptance issues.

Romania

Like in Greece and Croatia, bioenergy is not much in the news in Romania. Some justified concerns regarding illegal logging and high firewood consumption by households can be found, which may make the step to use additional woody biomass for energy somewhat risky. Bioenergy from non-woody resources, such as agricultural residues received positive media attention. In SmartCHP, the case study is linked to the use of non-woody biomass, namely corn stover, which is not expected to meet socio-political acceptance issues.

It is expected that it is possible to introduce SmartCHP technology without major social acceptance issues in Sweden, Croatia, Greece and Romania. The socio-political acceptance of bioenergy is very low in the Netherlands, making it - from a social acceptance point of view - a less attractive country for market introduction of SmartCHP technology.

4.2 Community acceptance

Due to the low response to the interviews, within the scope of this study, it was not possible to define a community acceptance strategy at country level. Below we link the relevance of the most prevailing concerns to bioenergy installations as found in Eswaralal et al. (2014) (See Table 3-5) with the SmartCHP system and make the following observations:

- Vibrations and noise from the plant were regarded relevant in all identified bioenergy plants. Given that SmartCHP systems include a diesel engine, it will be highly relevant to apply proper noise and vibration reduction measures.
- Visual effects were also regarded highly relevant and mentioned in 7 of the 8 cases. In case of SmartCHP the chimney may be visible from outside the building. Its design should fit well in the local environment and building architecture.
- Odour is mentioned five times, and already identified as a risk factor in our ad hoc analysis.
- Another issue mentioned five times is the possible negative impacts on property prices. This impact is expected to be limited if the SmartCHP system is not visible, and operates without significant odour, noise and vibrations.
- Local air pollution and traffic movements were issues of concern as well. Low emissions and emission reduction is an important research topic within

the SmartCHP project. Traffic movements to supply FPBO to the installation will be unavoidable.

- Fear for biodiversity impacts will be linked to biomass type used to produce the FPBO. This fear should in general be limited, especially as residues are used. Here also the socio-political acceptance of bioenergy in the focus country plays an important role.

In order to promote community acceptance in general, the SmartCHP systems have to be designed in such a way that it generates low noise (insulation of engine), low odour (vapour return system during unloading pyrolysis oil), low emissions (emission reduction equipment), and low visibility (modest chimney, underground tank). The storage tank should have the size of at least one truck load avoiding traffic movements. This way the Not In My BackYard (NIMBY) effect and related distributional justice issues can be minimised. Procedural justice, e.g. fair permit procedures, depends partly on the permitting process of the involved country. However, it is generally advised to communicate in a fair way - and in an early stage of the permit process - with the neighbouring community about the plans to install a SmartCHP system, and its impacts.

4.3 Market acceptance

As depicted in Figure 4-1, market acceptance depends on various factors including social acceptance and community acceptance factors, as further discussed below.

View decision makers and clients/users on benefits

Decision makers and users need to see the (environmental, social, hedonic, and financial) benefits from the use of SmartCHP technology. The biomass source of the pyrolysis oil determines an important part of the perceived environmental benefit. It should be clear that no stemwood/whole trees were used to produce pyrolysis oil. Being a legal prerequisite of the RED II, sustainability certification of pyrolysis oil can also be used to support its market acceptance. Social and hedonic benefits related to personal interest of the decision maker/user, social status, feel good, may be less relevant than in the consumer market, but will definitely play a role. Promotional aspects, positioning as being a pioneer, showing that the organisation cares for the environment, can form important motivations to use SmartCHP technologies. An attractive and clean-cut design can create the desire to own a system. Examples are the power wall of Tesla, and the Nest-thermostat. Pellet boilers often have a very modern appearance as well.

Financial feasibility

Financial feasibility depends on market conditions, bioenergy subsidies, which depend also on socio-political acceptance as shown in Figure 3-10. Further information is provided in the *Final SmartCHP Financial and economic analysis for different use cases including hybrid systems – publishable report* (SmartCHP Deliverable D6.6)

Low transaction costs, easy permits

For market acceptance, it is important that the hassles around the investment in SmartCHP technology is limited. Part of this form permit procedures, especially in

case an extensive environmental permit would be needed. The legal and permit requirements are further assessed in the SmartCHP *Assessment of legal and regulatory issues* (SmartCHP Deliverable D6.7). It is advised to provide permit application services to clients that do not want to go into the hassle of obtaining a permit for a relatively new technology that is also still new to permit authorities.

Product properties

Next to the environmental impacts the following product properties have to be considered in the design of the SmartCHP system:

- Functional reliability
- System lifetime
- Space requirements
- Safety
- Ease of use.

Reliability of energy systems is of utmost relevance. If the system is not 100% reliable, a backup system should be installed. It would also be a plus if the system could run on another (bio)fuel next to pyrolysis oil. A minimum system lifetime should be secured by providing guarantees for a certain period. Space requirements are important for most users, but also related to the specific group of users identified (e.g. greenhouses, hotels etc.). Safety of the system is highly important, and the supplier should be able to tackle all safety risks. Ease of use is particularly relevant if the user does not have a technical background and/or function. Given the size of the system, the final user cannot spend hours per day on the SmartCHP system. Hence, the automation of operation is key.

Trust in equipment and fuel suppliers

SmartCHP is a combination of a new technology with a new fuel. The Equipment and fuel suppliers should preferably have an established good reputation. Maybe the product could be sold under the flag of an existing well-known supplier of CHP systems.

4.4 Market introduction strategy

Product information

Since SmartCHP is a new technology, requiring a rather large investment, next to hedonic and normative motivations, there is a strong need for facts enabling a rational decision making. First, information on the product will be made available in a visually attractive brochure and on several websites. It should contain the following type of information:

- What is pyrolysis oil?
- Sustainability – all pyrolysis oil is produced from certified sustainable biomass.
- Advantages of pyrolysis oil compared to other fuels
- Environmental benefits – example calculations
- Economic benefits – example calculations
- Advantages compared to other biomass fuels.
- Technical description of the SmartCHP technology
- Emissions
- Advises for SmartCHP users:
 - what are the costs of using FPBO power and heat generation?
 - what should I consider when buying a SmartCHP system
 - what to take into account when installing a SmartCHP system in my home?
- Pyrolysis oil supplier information.

The information could be disseminated through social media and mass media where possible.

Specific information could be developed to address possible worries, fears and scepticisms that can arise with consumers on innovative technologies such as SmartCHP.

Start demonstration project and awareness campaign

Under attractive conditions, a number of say 3 – 5 pilot projects could be installed, and their performance carefully monitored. Some of the demonstrated installations should permanently be accessible for visits by interested decision makers and potential users, enabling them to see and touch the system. It will be possible to attract attention from mass media like newspapers, and (regional) television stations. The performance of the SmartCHP systems should already be secured at an earlier stage; if the demo would fail, this could lead to undesired negative attention. The demo may be a good opportunity to train installation companies, though.

Start a market introduction campaign

Once the demonstration has been running smoothly for a year or more, a marketing campaign could be started for the most promising target groups from the identified subsectors, i.e., from the tertiary, industrial, residential and agriculture sector. See SmartCHP Deliverable *D6.1 Market assessment* for a first assessment of the various subsectors.

The campaign should be well organised involving the SmartCHP system manufacturer, 2-3 installation companies that have been trained to install SmartCHP equipment, and possibly the pyrolysis oil producer. The marketing campaign can be developed by a marketing firm, coordinated by a dedicated marketer with a small team that has the overview on the messages and their distribution channels.

Maintain a high service level especially during the first years after market introduction

Failures of the installation need to be solved quickly, especially during the first years after the installation. It is recommended to provide a full-service package for the economic lifetime of the equipment, which gives users the certainty that the installation will always be operational.

Develop a strategy to cope with critical questions on sustainability

In some countries, like the Netherlands, the media can be rather negative about the sustainability of bioenergy. It is advised to develop a list of possible questions and answers on the sustainability of this application, for contact with the press. If needed such a list can be edited for placement on the website. Moreover, it is advised to develop a positive campaign on the environmental benefits of SmartCHP use, avoiding becoming too reactive and giving too much attention to negative voices.

Involve policy makers at national and regional level

It is very important that SmartCHP technology becomes a common element in renewable energy plans of national and regional authorities. This paves the way for support in the implementation phase, which could be financial support (e.g. subsidies on installations), being part of renewable energy promotion campaigns, and support in solving administrative and legal issues.

Get involved in local and regional renewable energy promotion platforms

Renewable energy platforms can support the introduction of the concept of Smart CHP technology. A good example of such an initiative is the Bioenergy Cluster of the Eastern Netherlands. This platform has good access to policy makers at province and regional level, and the companies that are members support each other.

5. Annex I

Country	Organization
Croatia	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Croatian Energy Regulatory Agency (HERA) 2. Croatian Energy Market Operator 3. Energy Institute Hrvoje Pozar 4. The Environmental Protection and Energy Efficiency Fund 5. Croatian Biomass Association (CROBIOM) 6. North-West Croatia Regional Energy Agency (REGEA) 7. Ministry of Environmental Protection and Energy 8. CROBIOM 9. UPUHH -ASSOCIATION OF ENTREPRENEURS IN THE HOSPITALITY 10. Croatian Chemical Society 11. Resalta 12. MGIPU- Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets 13. Two members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)
Greece	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ministry of the Environment and Energy 2. Ministry of Rural Development and Food 3. Center For Renewable Energy Sources- CRES 4. Hellenic Biomass association - Hellabiom 5. Regulatory Authority for Energy -RAE 6. CERTH - Centre for Research and Technology Hellas 7. BioCatPolymers 8. Archirodon 9. MAGIC 10. GRHOTELS 11. EEX 12. SIDENOR 13. HLV 14. SolBio-Rev 15. HELBIO 16. Five members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)
Sweden	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Ministry for the Environment and Energy 2. Swedish Bioenergy Association (SVEBIO) 3. Swedish Energy Agency 4. Swedish Wood Fuel Association 5. SalixEnergi 6. Ekma group 7. Candbio 8. Sekab 9. HSB 10. SVERIGES ALLMANNYTTA 11. Bostadsbolaget 12. Bostads AB Mimer 13. Gavlegårdarna 14. Halmstads Fastighets AB 15. VISITA 16. Swedish Chemical Society 17. Jernkontoret 18. Three members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)
Romania	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Romanian Energy Regulatory Authority (ANRE) 2. Ministry of Energy 3. Ministry of Agriculture and rural development 4. ROMANIAN RENEWABLE ENERGY ASSOCIATION - ROREA 5. Romanian Energy Center Association 6. Romanian Association of Biomass and Biogas -ARBIO 7. RABO 8. Casi Sociale ACUM 9. ROMPAP -Romanian Paper Association 10. UniRomSider 11. GREENCLUSTER 12. Energy Serv 13. Four members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)

Country	Organization	
Croatia	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Croatian Energy Regulatory Agency (HERA) 2. Croatian Energy Market Operator 3. Energy Institute Hrvoje Pozar 4. The Environmental Protection and Energy Efficiency Fund 5. Croatian Biomass Association (CROBIOM) 6. North-West Croatia Regional Energy Agency (REGEA) 7. Ministry of Environmental Protection and Energy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 8. CROBIOM 9. UPUHH -ASSOCIATION OF ENTREPRENEURS IN THE HOSPITALITY 10. Croatian Chemical Society 11. Resalta 12. MGIPU- Ministry of Physical Planning, Construction and State Assets 13. Two members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)
The Netherlands	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency 2. Bio-Economy Platform 3. Natuur & Milieu (Nature & Environment) 4. Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands (ECN) 5. Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Policy 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 6. KHN 7. Vastgoed Belang 8. NVM 9. Bond Precaire Woonvormen 10. VPN 11. CPM EUROPE 12. HoSt 13. Three members of ENVE Commission at the Committee of Regions (Direct contact)

6. Annex II

Name of interviewee:

Organization/ Company:

Position held within the Organization/ Company:

Comments/questions on presentation:

Interviews with policy makers, NGOs and end-users

- 1. Are lower GHG emissions in energy production a significant target for your country?**
- 2. How would you describe the state of energy production and distribution in your country at the moment? Do you believe there is room for improvement in the energy sector?**
- 3. Are there any specific targets related to bioenergy production or to its contribution to the energy mix in your country?**
- 4. Do you consider bioenergy production as a potential important contributor to the decarbonization of the energy system in your country?**
- 5. In your opinion, who should take the first step towards bioenergy production? (Provide examples: Public sector, energy producers/distributors, other)**
- 6. Are you aware of any bioenergy projects currently implemented in the country/region? (If yes, have they joined or are willing to join a CHP project)**
- 7. Are you familiar with the bio-CHP technology? And do you know its advantages?**

- 8. In your opinion, what is the influence of national/local policies on bioenergy deployment? And more specifically concerning urban planning and financing of bioenergy projects including CHP?**
- 9. Do you foresee any barriers or risks linked to the implementation of a bioenergy plant, and in particular bio-CHP plants? (If no specific response, mention options from below list. If specific response which does not include one of the options below, ask question about it)**
 - a. Cost**
 - b. Installation**
 - c. Performance**
 - d. Maintenance**
- 10. What motivation factors do you deem important to implement bio-energy projects? And which sector could make most use of it in your view?**
- 11. Are you aware of any facilitating conditions or incentives in place for bioenergy and more specifically bio-CHP plants development in your country?**

Questions for Municipalities

- 1. Is your municipality taking part in any initiative or accord related to climate mitigation? (Covenant of mayors, Green city accord, etc.)**
- 2. How important is the local production of green energy for you?**
- 3. How easy is it to get a permit for the implementation of such projects in your municipality?**
- 4. What is the influence of decisions of your municipality on bioenergy projects?**
- 5. Do you often communicate about renewable energies in general and bioenergy in particular? How would you grade the community's awareness about the topic?**
- 6. Are there any local initiatives supporting the consumer's transition to RE sources in your municipality?**

